

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D4.4 Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

WP4 – Engagement and motivation strategies for youth
participation

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Table of Contents

1	Executive summary	9
2	Introduction	10
3	Relevant Content Discovery	11
3.1	Post classification and filtering	11
3.2	Topic detection and mining	13
3.3	Content retrieval and ranking	23
4	Improved Audience Analysis	24
4.1	Relevant account discovery and ranking	24
4.1.1	Keyword selection & querying social media APIs	25
4.1.2	Account classification	26
4.1.3	Generating the final list of accounts	27
4.2	STEP audience analysis	28
4.2.1	Follower graph construction	28
4.2.2	Community detection and visualization	29
4.2.3	Communities around STEP Twitter account	29
4.2.3.1	Influential Twitter users in STEP network	31
4.2.3.2	Influential Twitter users that do not follow STEP	32
4.2.4	Communities around STEP pilots	33
4.3	Engagement measurements	38

5	User Interface Improvements	44
5.1	Redesign of pilots user interface.....	44
5.2	Improved user controls.....	50
5.2.1	New query facilities.....	50
5.2.2	Content scoring and filtering	51
5.3	New and improved visualizations	52
6	Integration and Pilot Support.....	53
6.1	Integration with e-participation module.....	53
6.1.1	Automated translation.....	53
6.1.2	Use of SMMT topics in e-participation module.....	54
6.2	Updated REST API	54
6.3	Performance optimizations.....	56
6.4	Pilot configuration.....	56
6.5	User training sessions	58
7	Evaluation	60
7.1	Pilot data analysis.....	60
7.2	User evaluation workshops.....	64
7.3	Teenagers’ questionnaire analysis	69
8	Conclusions and Future Work.....	72
9	References	73
10	Appendix I.....	74
11	Appendix II.....	89

Table of Figures

Table 1: First classifier details (English).....	12
Table 2: Second classifier details (English).....	12
Table 3: A few selected classification examples. The first four examples present cases of successful classification, while the last two examples present cases of failed classification.	12
Figure 1: Topics detected with LDA, from the posts in the collection of the EU pilot, related to climate change. The position of each topic is determined using Laplacian Eigenmaps. The size of the circles, corresponding to topics, is proportional to their prevalence $P(T)$, while their description is given in terms of the 6 most relevant words.....	15
Table 4: Top 5 Topics detected by LDA from the posts of the EU climate change dialogue, sorted by prevalence $P(T)$	16
Figure 2: Topics detected with NMF in the posts of the same collection as Figure 1.	17

Table 5: Top 5 Topics detected by NMF from the posts of the EU climate change dialogue, sorted by prevalence P(T).	17
Figure 3: Posts of the EU dialogue with respect to the LDA topic they most likely belong to. The position of the documents is decided by the t-SNE manifold learning method. For each topic in the legend (all topics correspond to the ones of Figure 1), the number of associated documents is also presented in the parenthesis.	19
Figure 4 Posts of the EU dialogue with respect to the NMF topic they most likely belong to.	20
Figure 5: LDA Topics extracted from the articles of the EU pilot climate change dialogue.....	21
Table 6: Top 5 Topics detected by LDA from the articles shared in the posts of EU climate change dialogue, sorted by prevalence P(T).....	22
Figure 6: Articles of the EU dialogue with respect to the LDA topic they most likely belong to. The position of the documents is decided by the t-SNE manifold learning method.	22
Figure 7: Relevance judgments of an item in respect to a collection related to climate change. The user can select a value in the range 1-5, with 1 corresponding to no relevance and 5 indicating high relevance.	23
Table 7: General concepts from STEP pilot dialogues.....	24
Table 8: List of keywords for account retrieval for each general concept	25
Table 9: Indicative examples of relevant and irrelevant accounts	27
Table 10: Account classifier training set size and accuracy.....	27
Figure 8: Visualization of different communities in the STEP followers of followers network.....	30
Figure 9: The Valdemoro accounts community of the STEP followers of followers network	30
Table 11: Influential accounts based of their incoming degree	31
Table 12: Most influential users that do not follow STEP account.....	32
Table 13: Seed accounts for STEP Pilot graph.....	33
Table 14: Top 5 account locations in each of the major discovered communities	34
Figure 10: STEP Pilot network communities	35
Table 15: The size of each discovered community.	35
Table 16: Follow connections between STEP Pilot communities.....	35
Figure 11: Follow connections between STEP Pilot communities. Bigger cycles represent bigger communities. Also, bold edges mean stronger connections between communities.....	36
Table 17: Tweet classification results	36
Table 18: Top 50 users based on the number of relevant tweets they posted.....	37
Table 19: Top 5 most discussed concepts per community	38
Figure 12: Post reach of STEP account from Facebook insights page.....	40
Figure 13: Audience demographics of STEP account from Facebook insights page	40
Figure 14: Tweet reach of STEP account from Twitter analytics page	41
Figure 15: Audience demographics of STEP account from Twitter analytics page	41
Table 20: Top 15 retweeters of STEP account	42
Table 21: Most active communities based on the number of retweeter	42
Figure 16: Retweet and reach analysis of 141 STEP posts. Scatter plot of posts' reach on the STEP follower graph versus their retweets.....	43
Figure 17: Stats Widget.....	44
Figure 18: Users Widget.....	45
Figure 19: Timeline Widget.....	45
Figure 20: Posts Widget	46
Figure 21: Articles Widget.....	46
Figure 22: Platforms Widgets.....	47
Figure 23: Tags Widget	47
Figure 24: Concepts Widget.....	48
Figure 25: Map Widget	48
Figure 26: Overview of the Pilot Specific User Interface.....	49

Figure 27: Widget to support the insertion of logical expressions to define a collection	50
Figure 28: Widget for specifying the target geo-location for a collection.....	50
Figure 29: User/Item Exclusion	51
Figure 30: Exclude User	51
Figure 31: Exclude Keyword.....	51
Figure 32: Animation of Entities	52
Figure 33: List View	52
Table 22: Translation direction values	53
Figure 34: Translation of posts.....	54
Table 23: New methods included in the REST API of social media monitoring tool.....	55
Table 24: Input configuration for each of the dialogue in STEP platform.The keywords and accounts of each of the dialogues were provided by the corresponding pilot.	56
Figure 35: Educational videos of the STEP SMMT on YouTube.....	59
Table 25: Summary of the dialogues used for topic detection. The posts corresponding only to original content after discarding shares and retweets. Articles have been extracted from the URLs in these posts.	61
Table 26: Most prevalent topic detected in the posts of the two dialogues of EU pilot.....	62
Table 27: Most prevalent topic detected in two of the dialogues of EU pilot.	63
Figure 36: The UI of TAGBOARD. Sample Results for #natura2000	65
Figure 37: How do users perceive TAGBOARD's user interface as compared to the STEP Social Media Monitoring Tool's interface	66
Table 28: TAGBOARD's UI evaluation. Average scores and standard deviation.....	66
Figure 38 : Relevance assessments of SMMT results.....	67
Figure 39 : STEP SMMT - Evaluation of the widgets.....	67
Figure 40: How understandable are the various widgets of the tool.....	68
Figure 41: Rating of the usefulness of the filters	68
Figure 42: Where you able to find interested topics related to the environment within SMMT? (Si: Yes, No: NO, N/S: NA).....	70
Figure 43: To what extent do you agree with the following statements. From left to right: (1) Overall, I am satisfied with how easy it is to use SMMT (2) I was able to complete the tasks and scenarios quickly using SMMT (3) I believe I could become productive quickly using SMMT (4) Whenever I made a mistake using the system I could recover easily and quickly	70
Figure 44: To what extent do you agree with the following statements. From left to right: (5) The organization of information on the SMMT screens was clear (6) The interface was pleasant (7) I can count on the information I get on this system (8) The information on this system is valuable (9) The results are very relevant to my search (10) Filters work great (11) I will likely suggest SMMT to a friend.....	71
Table 29: Widgets' Weighted Average Table	71
Table 30: First classifier details (Greek)	74
Table 31: Second classifier details (Greek).....	74
Table 32: First classifier details (Spanish).....	74
Table 33: Second classifier details (Spanish).....	74
Table 34: First classifier details (Italian)	74
Table 35: Second classifier details (Italian)	74
Table 36: First classifier details (Turkish)	75
Table 37: Second classifier details (Turkish).....	75
Table 38: First classifier details (Catalan)	75
Table 39: Second classifier details (Catalan)	75
Table 40: List of keywords for post retrieval for each concept.....	75
Table 41: Influential accounts based on their incoming degree	76
Table 42: Most influential users that do not follow STEP account.....	78
Table 43: Top 50 users based on the number of relevant tweets they posted.....	80

Table 44: Top 5 users that post relevant content per community.....	82
Table 45: Top 5 users that post concept related content per concept.....	84
Figure 45: The Sustainable development goals accounts community of the STEP network.....	86
Figure 46: The Entrepreneurs - media influencers accounts community of the STEP network.....	86
Figure 47: The Greek accounts community of the STEP network.....	87
Figure 48: The European projects - Innovation 1 accounts community of the STEP network.....	87
Figure 49: The European projects – Innovation B accounts community of the STEP network.....	88
Figure 50: The Youth job opportunities accounts community of the STEP network.....	88

1 Executive summary

This deliverable provides an account of the development and testing of the Social Media Monitoring Tool (SMMT) that has been carried out during the second period of the STEP project.

During this period, a number of improvements and extensions have been implemented following an agile and iterative development process, in which the tool capabilities were demonstrated and tested by end users - Public Administration (PA) officers and young citizens from the pilot municipalities - and feedback was collected by the development team in order to implement improvements and to add newly requested capabilities. Much of the newly added capabilities and the results reported here required evaluating and integrating numerous state-of-the-art advances and outcomes from the research area of social media mining, especially with respect to the areas of text classification, topic mining (Section 3) and social network analysis (Section 4). Moreover, the PA view of the tool user interface underwent a redesign and reimplementations to make its use more appealing and intuitive (Section 5).

In addition to the new research and development work, considerable effort was dedicated to the support of integration to the platform and its appropriate configuration for the STEP pilots (Section 6). Finally, the SMMT was evaluated in a number of ways (Section 7): a) by assessing the quality of output of its individual components (e.g. classification of social media posts), b) by conducting a data-driven study focused on the STEP pilot sites, and c) by a user study involving several PA officers and young citizens of the STEP pilot sites. The conclusions of these evaluation activities have made clear that the SMMT offers a rich set of capabilities for collecting and making sense of large amounts of topic-focused social media content and for analyzing the social media audience and their engagement around issues of public concern. At the same time, the evaluation outcomes have pointed to areas of potential improvement that could render the tool more valuable for end users and could benefit its adoption and exploitation (Section 0).

It is worth noting that a public technical demonstration of the SMMT has been offered in the context of the upcoming Internet Science conference (November 2017), and a technical description has been included in the proceedings of the conference in the form of a paper (Schinas et al., 2017). The tool is available online¹ and its source code is maintained on GitHub².

¹¹ <http://smtt.step.green>

² <https://github.com/MKLab-ITI/mmdemo-dockerized>

2 Introduction

The focus during the second project period was to align the STEP Social Media Monitoring Tool (SMMT) with the end users' needs, aiming at better achieving its primary objectives, i.e. the monitoring of social media for analyzing discussions related to environmental and regional issues, and for better understanding the audience of social media campaigns and user communities. To this end, the SMMT development team adopted an iterative approach, in which improvements and new features were added to the tool and feedback was collected by relevant partners (Public Authority (PA) officers from pilot sites, STEP integration team, and project coordinator) with the goal of further refining and fine tuning the tool output.

One of the key issues that have been studied during this period concerns the improvement of relevance for the collected content and the automated extraction of topics of interest from large amounts of social media discussions. To this end, we devised a set of STEP-oriented concept/topic classifiers with the goal of discarding posts that are irrelevant to the core STEP topics (environment, sustainability, climate, etc.) and to classify the relevant ones into a set of general topics of interest. This addition benefited SMMT in multiple ways: a) resulted in improved quality of content and thus higher end user satisfaction, b) led to the removal of a sizeable amount of irrelevant posts, thus reducing storage and indexing requirements and improving response times, c) enabled the filtering of content based on concept (i.e. more powerful browsing capabilities for end users), and d) made possible the characterization of monitored discussions and user communities in terms of broad topics of interest. Furthermore, state-of-the-art topic detection and visualization methods were employed with the goal of studying the discussed topics in large-scale collections of social media posts. As a last activity towards improved content relevance, we describe the implementation of a feedback collection and relevance ranking mechanism. All aforementioned advances are detailed in Section 3.

A second area of interest has been the implementation of methods for analyzing the audience of social media campaigns and discussions and for discovering social media accounts and communities of interest. To this end, we devised a mechanism for automatically discovering social media accounts of relevance to the STEP topics using an automated query, aggregation and classification pipeline. Subsequently, we employed a social network analysis approach to analyze the audience of social media accounts of relevance to STEP. In particular, we made use of the Louvain community detection algorithm with the goal of extracting communities of Twitter accounts that belong to the extended follower base (2-hop neighbourhood) of the STEP project account and of accounts of relevance for the pilot sites. In addition to discovering topically-focused communities, we leveraged the 2-hop follower network to discover social media accounts with high potential influence. Finally, we employed methods for measuring the engagement of social media audience with the content posted by STEP. All of the above aspects are presented in detail in Section 4.

Following the feedback we received from pilot end users, we carried out a redesign of the SMMT user interface with a focus on facilitating access to the tool results and making its usage easier for non-experts. In addition to the redesign, several new visualizations and features were added, including new query facilities, feedback mechanisms, etc. These updates are presented in Section 5. Activities related to the support of pilots, including configuration of data sources, API extensions and updates, and execution of training activities (material and workshops) are documented in Section 6.

Finally, the results of an end-to-end evaluation, comprising a data-driven study on social media data collected from the pilots and a user-centred evaluation workshop involving end users from the pilot sites are presented in Section 7, while conclusions and planned activities beyond the end of the project are presented in Section 8.

3 Relevant Content Discovery

One of the key goals during the second period of the project was to develop methods that would improve the quality and relevance of the collected content and would help the development team and ultimately the PA officers better understand the topics discussed in social media. Both of the aforementioned goals emerged as a response to early feedback received from the STEP pilot partners, which highlighted the need for improved relevance in the collected content. To address these goals, we devised a machine learning-based pipeline for relevance and topic-based classification (Section 3.1), two methods for topic mining and visualization (Section 3.2), and a mechanism for end users to explicitly provide feedback on the relevance of fetched content in order to affect its ranking (Section 3.3).

3.1 Post classification and filtering

In this section, we describe in detail the employed methodology for developing robust mechanisms for classifying social media posts into classes/concepts of interest. The list consists of the following environment-related concepts: ecology, eco-efficiency, climate change, waste, water protection, environmental policy, land degradation, urban environment, which were defined in collaboration with Draxis. To train a classifier, we first needed to annotate a number of examples per concept. To this end, the first step focused on the use of concept-related keywords³ (again defined with the help of Draxis) to retrieve relevant social media content. This was achieved by using the statuses/filter endpoint⁴ of the Twitter API (previously referred as the Twitter Steaming API). This endpoint retrieves in real time tweets using a set of keywords as input. We used the aforementioned list of keywords as input to the filter API endpoint for a period of a week (18-25/9) and retrieved more than 100K posts, which were then stored in a local database.

Having collected a large amount of training samples (posts), we proceeded to the manual annotation of a subset of them. We randomly fetched tweets from the database and assigned them the most appropriate class. This task was carried out in two stages. In the first, we assigned corresponding labels to each post depending on whether the post is relevant or irrelevant with the environmental topics. If the post was annotated as relevant in the first stage, we proceeded to the second stage, in which we assigned the label of the corresponding class. In cases where a post was found to be related to more than one topics of interest, we created an equal number of training samples, one for each related topic. Through this process, we manually annotated 3000 Twitter posts.

The purpose of employing two annotation stages was to create a two-step classification method. In the first step, the first classifier decides if the post is relevant or not. Table 1 presents the evaluation of the first classifier. If the post is classified as relevant, then the second classifier will assign the most probable class or classes. Table 2 presents the evaluation of the second classifier, and Table 3 contains some examples that illustrate the classification mechanism. For each classifier the post text was preprocessed by applying stemming and stop-word removal and represented using a tf-idf bag-of-words representation. As classification algorithm, we used an L2-regularized L2-loss Support Vector Machine (the LibLinear⁵ implementation) with default parameters. To make classifiers more accurate, we set the probability threshold to the first classifier to be 0.6. For the second classifier, given that we were interested in multi-label classification, we found that to obtain higher recall, it was better to assign classes to posts that have probability larger than 0.2.

³ The list of keywords per concept/topic can be found on: <http://goo.gl/V3fmDt>

⁴ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/tweets/filter-realtime/api-reference/post-statuses-filter.html>

⁵ <https://www.csie.ntu.edu.tw/~cjlin/liblinear/>

Table 1: First classifier details (English)

Firstclassifier	# examples	Precision	Recall
relevant	1500	84.3%	86.7%
irrelevant	1500	85.8%	83.3%

Table 2: Second classifier details (English)

Secondclassifier	# examples	Precision	Recall
ecology	180	57.2%	56.3%
eco-efficiency	180	63.2%	61.7%
climatechange	220	72.1%	74%
waste	200	63.1%	64.2%
waterprotection	200	54.2%	53.3%
environmentalpolicy	160	66%	62.4%
landdegradation	180	54.2%	52.9%
urbanenvironment	180	67.2%	65.2%

Table 3: A few selected classification examples. The first four examples present cases of successful classification, while the last two examples present cases of failed classification.

Posttext	Firstclassifier	SecondClassifier	Result with probability threshold > 0.2
Air pollution and deforestation are destroying the planet	Irrelevant -> 0.002 Relevant -> 0.998	waste -> 0.004 ecology -> 0.0250 land_degradation -> 0.211 climate_change -> 0.707 environmental_policy -> 0.005 eco_efficiency -> 0.0116 water_protection -> 0.0099 urban_environment -> 0.0238	climate_change land_degradation
Gargling with warm water and salt then having tea with honey helps	Irrelevant -> 0.8892 Relevant -> 0.1108	-	-
Nitrite pollution puts waters at risk	Irrelevant -> 0.0515 Relevant -> 0.9485	waste -> 0.0454 ecology -> 0.2638 land_degradation -> 0.0130 climate_change -> 0.1359 environmental_policy -> 0.0235 eco_efficiency -> 0.0265 water_protection -> 0.3979 urban_environment -> 0.0940-	water_protection ecology
What a quality stream watching winner dancing in their chairs as they wait for their turn to get on air	Irrelevant -> 0.9021 Relevant -> 0.0979	-	-
I usually forget to water the plants	Irrelevant -> 0.3837 Relevant -> 0.6163	waste -> 0.0130 ecology -> 0.0157 land_degradation -> 0.0625 climate_change -> 0.0128 environmental_policy -> 0.0165 eco_efficiency -> 0.0444 water_protection -> 0.8228 urban_environment -> 0.0123	water_probtection
Factories make atmosphere worse day after day	Irrelevant -> 0.6832 Relevant -> 0.3168	-	-

To deal with languages other than English (Greek, Spanish, Italian, Turkish, Catalan), we translated all training samples into other languages. Evaluation results for these languages are presented in Appendix I.

The outcome of the classifier is used in the social media monitoring tool in two ways: first, as a means to discard items/posts that are irrelevant to environmental issues and second, as an additional filter for items in the UI based on the detected concepts. The first is based on the outcome of the first classifier. Posts with low confidence score, i.e. $\text{relevant} < 0.6$, are totally discarded, without being stored and indexed by the tool. For the remaining posts, we keep posts, where the detected concepts have sufficiently high probability (> 0.2) and add the respective scores in a field named “concepts”. This field is also indexed in Solr to be used for filtering during retrieval. For example, if the user seeks to find posts related only to land degradation in a collection with a broader topic, then the query “concepts”: “land_degradation” is used as an additional filter query in Solr.

3.2 Topic detection and mining

The topic detection method that has been integrated in the social media monitoring tool during the first period, is based on the Search Results Clustering Engine supported by Solr⁶. Given a collection, the input of this module is the set of relevant posts returned by the tool. The output consists of a partial clustering of these results, based on the Lingo clustering algorithm (Osiński et al, 2004). Each cluster contains a set of posts, and a label that describes the topic of the cluster. These labels are then used as the options of a filter in the social media monitoring tool, to narrow down the set of collection-related posts upon the selection of a topic label.

Apart from clustering the posts of collections around topics and integrating the results in the tool, we also conducted a set of experiments using more advanced topic detection techniques to collections created by the pilot users of STEP with the goal of refining the quality of the extracted results. More specifically, for each collection with a sufficient number of items (more than 500 posts), we applied Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (Blei et al, 2003) and Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) (Lee and Sebastian, 1999). We used the topics, topic-words distributions, and topic-document associations from the application of LDA and NMF, in order to first interpret the meaning of topics and to estimate their prevalence, then to identify and visualize hidden relations between topics and posts, and finally to give the option to users for more efficient filtering and ranking of posts.

In both approaches, the first step focuses on the creation of a documents-terms matrix containing the counts of each term in each of the documents/posts in the collection. Given that many of the terms appear in only a few documents, and each of the documents contains only a small portion of the terms, this matrix is very sparse. For that reason, we keep only terms that appear at least in 10 documents. We also discard terms appearing in more than 80% of the documents as non-informative. This limits the vocabulary to a fixed vocabulary of V terms, resulting in an $N \times V$ document-term matrix, where N is the number of documents. Then, we apply either LDA or NMF by setting the number of topics to $K = \min(40, \sqrt{N}, V - 1)$. Each of the generated topics is associated with the words in the vocabulary with a conditional probability $P(w|T)$ indicating the likelihood that the observed topic T was generated by the latent word w . The *prevalence*, i.e. the importance of each topic T , is estimated with the marginal probability $P(T)$ calculated using the topics-words association matrix returned by LDA and NMF. At this point, we should mention that NMF does not return probabilities as it is not a probabilistic approach as LDA, but a matrix decomposition method applied on the document-term matrix. However, we normalize the results of NMF, which permits us to treat them as probabilities and apply the procedure presented next, in a similar manner as LDA.

⁶ <http://project.carrot2.org/>

As most of the words in a topic T have low conditional probability, we keep only a subset of words per topic to represent them in a meaningful way. For that purpose, we used two metrics to sort and keep words: the conditional probability $P(w|T)$ and the word-topic relevance metric proposed by Sievert and Shirley (2014). More precisely the relevance of a word w to a topic T is defined as:

$$r(w, T) = \lambda P(w|T) + (1 - \lambda) \frac{P(w|T)}{P(w)}$$

The second part of the equation corresponds to the increase of the word probability in the specific topic compared to the marginal probability $P(w)$. In other words, this part boosts the terms that are important within the topic in comparison to their global importance. Using $\lambda=1$, the relevance is reduced to the topic-conditional probability $P(w|T)$. In our case we set $\lambda=0.6$ as suggested by Sievert and Shirley (2014). Also, to describe the whole collection, we use the word saliency method proposed by Chuang et al (2012). To calculate word saliency, we first calculate the “distinctiveness” of each word w as the Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence between the conditional probability $P(T|w)$ and the marginal probability of topics $P(T)$:

$$distinctiveness(w) = \sum_T P(T|w) \log \frac{P(T|w)}{P(T)}$$

Then, the saliency of w is defined as the product of the marginal word probability $P(w)$ and its distinctiveness.

$$saliency(w) = P(w) * distinctiveness(w)$$

Each document in the collection is modeled as a mixture of the detected topics. However, the mixture of topics for some of the documents might be quite vague as topic modeling techniques such as LDA and NMF are optimized for long text, consisting of multiple topics. However, in the case of social media data, where the content is quite short, published posts are usually associated with a single topic. To this end, we use the entropy of the topic mixture to keep only the items for which the associations to topics are localized to only few. More formally, given a document D and a mixture of topics P_D we calculate entropy as:

$$entropy(P_D) = \sum_{k=0}^K p_k \log_k(p_k)$$

where p_k is the probability that document D is associated with topic $k \in K$. We keep only documents having low entropy i.e. less than 0.4. In this way, most of the remaining documents are associated with a single topic with a probability higher than 0.5.

To visualize topics, we tried several manifold learning and dimensionality reduction methods to reduce the dimension of topics from V (i.e. the length of the vocabulary) to 2 dimensions. More precisely, we applied Multi-Dimensional Scaling (MDS) (Borg and Groenen, 2005), Laplacian Eigenmaps (LEs) (Ng et al, 2002), t-SNE (Maaten and Hinton, 2008), PCA, Isomap (Tenenbaum et al, 2000) and Locally Linear Embedding (LLE) (Roweis and Saul, 2000). From a qualitative evaluation of the results, we concluded that in the case of topics, LEs give the best visualization, while preserving the topic structure by mapping topics with similar word distribution to closer points. Apart from its positioning in this 2-dimensional space, each topic is depicted with a circle with size proportional to its prevalence, i.e. its marginal probability $P(T)$. Figure 1 depicts the topics detected by LDA from the posts of a dialogue created by the EU pilot of STEP (focused on climate change). Table 4 presents the five topics with the highest prevalence $P(T)$. Each topic is represented using the 6 most relevant terms. We also include the most relevant post per topic, according to the conditional probability $P(D|T)$. Figure 2 depicts topics for the same dialogue, detected by applying NMF. It is worth noting that NMF produces topics with

equivalent prevalence as shown in Figure 2, contrary to LDA (Figure 1), where prevalence varies significantly from topic to topic. In both cases however, the topics can be used upon selection as filters, to retrieve content from a collection only related to a specific topic. In the same way, instead of evaluating single posts, irrelevant or noisy topics can be used for the exclusion of whole sets of posts from the original collection.

Figure 1: Topics detected with LDA, from the posts in the collection of the EU pilot, related to climate change. The position of each topic is determined using Laplacian Eigenmaps. The size of the circles, corresponding to topics, is proportional to their prevalence $P(T)$, while their description is given in terms of the 6 most relevant words.

From Table 4

and Table 5 one may conclude that the prevalence $P(T)$ of a topic T is not directly correlated with the number of posts associated with it. For example, a topic with a high number of posts can have lower prevalence compared to a topic associated with less posts, and vice versa. This happens because prevalence, which as mentioned before is the marginal probability $P(T)$, is calculated from the term-topic association matrix and the corresponding probabilities. Thus, the topics that have high prevalence are those associated with terms of high probability. In this way, topics with many associated posts may have a low prevalence if these posts contain irrelevant or insignificant terms.

Table 4: Top 5 Topics detected by LDA from the posts of the EU climate change dialogue, sorted by prevalence $P(T)$.

Topic	Terms of high relevance	Relevant post	$P(T)$	Posts
4	change climate latest daily necessary prevent	The latest The Climate Change Mitigation Daily! https://t.co/vg7MWernwp Thanks to @CntrClimSec @JGRcapital #climate #climatechange	0.118	168
7	need billions costing act gao heat	GAO: #Climatechange already costing US billions in losses https://t.co/MlexM2rwYW via @YahooFinance	0.044	26
13	nature don best care home agriculture	If We Don't Take Care of Nature, Nature Will Take Care of Us: https://t.co/0cHNuzvkPR #climatechange #climateaction https://t.co/tM9HhCRYlu	0.039	25
2	trees food paris reducing security syria	The U.S. is now one of two nations rejecting the Paris climate deal. The other is Syria. #ClimateChange is real. https://t.co/UtjFJvnBxj	0.036	55
38	report power isreal coal solar levels	We are living with #climatechange now. From drought in Siria to Sea level rise affecting #Thames #floodplain\u2026 https://t.co/WPJ4dEfsBn	0.035	27

- 0 - climate necessary workshop damage tips building
- 1 - girls proper enable oecd articles ensure
- 2 - latest daily mikeblloomberg thanks justice sustainability
- 3 - new zealand york flood city hurricanes
- 4 - grilled sounds roasted toasted chief imf
- 5 - tipacorp reading ease worth reducing vegan
- 6 - global warming ready oct south movement
- 7 - cancels epa blocks speaking agency conference
- 8 - change heard awareness women coral unambitious
- 9 - billions costing losses gao taxpayers nbcnews
- 10 - world rest series starting wildlife al
- 11 - ends unless levels coal power sea
- 12 - action auditor congressional little consequences nytimes
- 13 - learn unit emission gases consumers line
- 14 - acidification ocean year marine deadly threat
- 15 - nature emerson rules walk muir mother
- 16 - tree reason prepared like autumn stand
- 17 - energy renewable clean shift sector increases
- 18 - plan strategic interior scrubs department ve
- 19 - electric study diesel cars gas finds
- 20 - real permafrost investors convinced terrifying addressing
- 21 - continents today day international updates funds
- 22 - news north good used india thank
- 23 - time approach focused hackathon largest support
- 24 - people invest indigenous steps fight biodiversity
- 25 - science maybe sides true jpholdren studies
- 26 - lawson lord apologises sceptic interview bbc
- 27 - extreme weather events frequent severe long
- 28 - mistake readings water major temperature worse
- 29 - years service humanity celebrate essential tomorrow
- 30 - arctic acidic threaten oceans affect affecting
- 31 - cities joins accord hall mayors driving
- 32 - food need availability faoknowledge security heart
- 33 - future create inequality unep dark way
- 34 - planet stupidest creatures doubt healthy preserve
- 35 - trees slow grow plant leaves fuller
- 36 - earth yes john nasa man david
- 37 - carbon zero emissions low transition focus
- 38 - trump argues accountability government office act
- 39 - resist remember yrs sandy demand fall

Figure 2: Topics detected with NMF in the posts of the same collection as Figure 1.

Table 5: Top 5 Topics detected by NMF from the posts of the EU climate change dialogue, sorted by prevalence P(T).

Topic	Words of high relevance	Relevant post	P(T)	Posts
38	trump argues accountability government office act	#COP23 opens in less than 3 weeks! More about the agenda and preparations here: https://t.co/pNRA6JGw9T\u00a0\u2026 #climatechange #ParisAgreement	0.033	255
11	ends unless levels coal power sea	Mountain glaciers shrinking across the West\n https://t.co/8OnwenoFMc\n#climatechange	0.032	213
21	continents today day international updates funds	This morning @basch_gottlieb President of @ecaf_ca explaining #ConservationAgriculture benefits for #ClimateChange\u2026 https://t.co/JKzW5OqoFY	0.032	265
1	proper enable oecd articles ensure girls	@COP22 @OECD @UNFCCC, ensure that Articles 11 & 12 on girls education get the proper resources to enable #climateaction	0.030	115
32	food need availability	BE THERE: Everyone Matters!	0.029	233

	faoknowledge security heart	https://t.co/5VDD2EQYZa \n#diversity #inclusion #climatechange #Spirituality\u2026 https://t.co/bezv4ZAf3V		
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To visualize the documents with respect to the topics they are associated with, we opted for the use of the t-SNE algorithm, as it led to a more natural grouping of documents compared to LEs or the rest of the dimensionality reduction methods. Using t-SNE we transform the documents from a K -dimension space to a 2-dimensional space. The intuition is that documents associated with the same topics, will end up closer in the new space. Figure 3 depicts the posts of the EU pilot dialogue after the application of t-SNE on the LDA topic vectors. The color of each document D in the figure represents the topic with the higher conditional probability $P(T|D)$. In the same way, Figure 4 depicts the same posts with respect to the NMF results. Comparing the two figures, one may conclude that in the case of LDA more posts are discarded as irrelevant, which results in fewer associations with topics. On the other hand, in the case of NMF most of the input posts are kept. This has to do mainly with the way that LDA and NMF work. Due to the Dirichlet prior assumptions made by LDA, document-topic associations tend to be smoother compared to NMF, which leads to a sparser association matrix.

As shown in Figure 3, posts associated with different topics are placed in distinct parts of the diagram. Also, the density of topics varies significantly, indicating the different degree of coherence in them. Topics consisting of posts with similar content (e.g. near duplicates due to sharing and retweeting) are depicted in a denser way and the corresponding posts are placed in a small area. For example, topic 27 in Figure 1 and Figure 3, is about action days organized globally in order to prevent climate change. This topic consists mainly from posts that are near duplicates or use many common words to describe the same aspect, i.e. the promotion of that type of events. A typical post of this topic is: "[#stopfundingfossilfuels](#) day of action 14th November [#climatechange](#) read link more info <http://stopfundingfossils.org>". In contrast, topics with more heterogeneous content occupy a wider area in the figure as in the case of topic 2, which is related to the rejection of Paris climate agreement by US and Syria. This topic consists of posts that exhibit more variations in their content, as different users use different vocabulary to describe the aspect from different viewpoints. On the other hand, in NMF results we can observe that almost for all the topics, the associated posts have a higher degree of diversity. This happens because, as NMF keeps more documents compared to LDA, many of these documents end up to topics that in the case of LDA were consisting mainly of near duplicates. In this way, NMF gives more diverse topics, but at the expense of noise (irrelevant content).

Figure 3: Posts of the EU dialogue with respect to the LDA topic they most likely belong to. The position of the documents is decided by the t-SNE manifold learning method. For each topic in the legend (all topics correspond to the ones of Figure 1), the number of associated documents is also presented in the parenthesis.

Topics 7 and 13 (

Table 4), related to the economic cost of climate change and actions against it respectively, have a prevalence value (0.044 and 0.039 respectively), marginally higher than topic 2 (0.036), which is related to the rejection of the Paris agreement by US and Syria. However, topic 2 have more than twice the associated posts of topics 7 and 13 (55 posts compared to 26 and 25). From Figure 3 we can see that topics 7 and 13 are more packed, while topic 2 spreads aout indicating more diverse content, due to different posts commenting on the Paris agreement rejection. In other words, given topics with comparable prevalence, topics with more documents tend to have more diverse content. In the case of topic 4 which consists of posts from news sources about the mitigation of climate change, and is also the most prevalent topic in Table 4, we can see that most of the related posts are placed in the bottom left quarter of Figure 3 (around point [-20, -10]). However, there are some posts quite far away in the bottom

right quarter (purple points around [40, -30]), indicating that these topics, i.e. topics having a large number of associated documents, are quite generic and could be separated in finer topics.

Figure 4 Posts of the EU dialogue with respect to the NMF topic they most likely belong to.

Given the limited textual content of social media items, it is not surprising that some of the topics detected by LDA or NMF are overwhelmed by noisy terms, which makes their interpretation a difficult task. Also, the brevity of social media posts, especially Twitter, often leads either to the detection of merged topics (i.e. two different topics merged into one) or to their fragmentation (i.e. the same topic is split over two or more topics). This is caused because in short texts the text overlap is more likely to be high even in the case of different topics. For example, in the case of the climate change dialogue, many of the posts are annotated with hashtags like #climatechange, #climateaction and #climate. These tags, being quite generic, are common even across posts associated with different aspects/topics. Thus, the existence of such terms may lead to the merging of these posts into a single topic because of their high textual overlap. On the other hand, posts that are associated with the same topic but use a different vocabulary usually end up being fragmenting across more than one topics.

To overcome these issues, we also investigated how the URLs shared through social media can be leveraged to improve topic detection. For the URLs contained in the posts of a collection, we first tried to

identify those that point to articles, and then to extract the title and text of these articles. For that purpose, we used the Newspaper3k library⁷ that supports article extraction from HTML content. As many different URLs may point to the same article, we used the MinHash algorithm to calculate a signature for each article based on its textual content, to keep only unique articles, since identical or similar articles have the same signature. Given a set of articles with textual content (the title and body of the article), we apply a similar approach as in the social media items. We tried both LDA and NFM, but in this case, we let documents be associated with more than one topic, by removing the entropy-based filter applied in the posts. We visualize topics detected in articles in a similar way as the topics extracted from the social media posts. For example, Figure 5 and Figure 6 depict the topics detected by LDA and NMF in the articles shared within the EU climate change dialogue. To represent topics, we used a subset of words based on the words saliency and on the topic-specific probabilities. To visualize articles, we used a similar approach as in the visualization of posts, although the same article might be associated with multiple topics. For this reason, we choose to color each article D by using the topic that maximizes the probability posterior probability $P(T|D)$.

Figure 5: LDA Topics extracted from the articles of the EU pilot climate change dialogue.

Figure 5 depicts the topics detected by the application of LDA in the articles extracted from the climate change dialogue, while Figure 6 depicts these articles using t-SNE. A first observation that can be made by comparing the topics extracted from posts to the ones extracted from articles, is that the latter exhibit higher diversity due to the larger vocabulary in articles. Also, the prevalence of topics in articles is more

⁷ <http://newspaper.readthedocs.io>

skewed with some topics being much more important than the remaining. From Figure 6 we can also conclude that topics are more diverse by inspecting the size of the areas covered by each topic. Most of the topics are expanded in a wide area, indicating that article-derived topics exhibit notable variations.

Table 6: Top 5 Topics detected by LDA from the articles shared in the posts of EU climate change dialogue, sorted by prevalence P(T).

Topic	Words of high relevance	Relevant Article	P(T)	Articles
12	renewables pipeline helm turbines incentives achieving	Reaction: Dieter Helm’s ‘least cost’ ideas for meeting the UK’s climate targets http://ift.tt/2gNrqqp	0.284	771
36	sandy melting reefs sheet atmospheric coral	Climate change may take a heavy toll on Greek GDP, land	0.276	655
11	nsw captain lagoon sydney flight straw	Woman is only passenger on holiday jet	0.082	304
30	narragansett epa estuary borden pruit inslee	EPA says 3 scientists won’t discuss climate change at R.I. conference	0.069	215
2	annemariayritys gcctthinkacttank yritys gender peoples networking	Global Climate Change Think & Act Tank	0.065	290

Figure 6: Articles of the EU dialogue with respect to the LDA topic they most likely belong to. The position of the documents is decided by the t-SNE manifold learning method.

3.3 Content retrieval and ranking

After its extension, SMMT end users can give feedback on the relevance of content with respect to a collection of interest through an appropriate user control (Figure 7). Relevance judgments are in the range 1-5, with 1 corresponding to no relevance and 5 indicating high relevance. These are then used to re-rank the results of the collection by boosting items more similar to the items annotated as highly relevant, i.e. the items annotated with a relevance signal higher than 3. More precisely, given a set of relevant items, the original query is expanded by using the RM3 variant of the relevance language models presented in the approach by Lavrenko and Croft (2011).

Figure 7: Relevance judgments of an item in respect to a collection related to climate change. The user can select a value in the range 1-5, with 1 corresponding to no relevance and 5 indicating high relevance.

Given a query $Q = q_1 q_2 \dots q_k$, the original model uses the top- N ranked documents as a pseudo-relevance feedback to expand Q by including other terms. In our case, we use only the direct feedback provided by users. Given a collection, a query Q and a set of items R with high relevance ($rel > 3$), we estimate a language model for each term w using the following formula:

$$P(w|R) = \frac{\sum_{D \in R} P(w|D)P(Q|D)}{\sum_{D \in R} P(Q|D)}$$

$P(Q|D)$ is estimated by the $\text{score}(D, Q)$ between the document D and the query Q , returned originally by Solr. For the estimation of $P(w|D)$ we use the following linear interpolation technique

$$P(w|D) = a \frac{tf(w, D)}{\sum_u tf(u, D)} + (1 - a)P(w|G)$$

where $tf(w, D)$ is the frequency of a term w in document D , and $P(w|G)$ is the frequency of w in the whole collection divided by the total number of terms. Then, we sort terms in $P(w|R)$ in descending order and keep only the top M of them. Finally, we interpolate the terms of original query Q with the top terms of the relevance model $P(w|R)$:

$$P'(w|R) = \lambda P(w|R) + (1 - \lambda)P(w|Q)$$

Note that negative judgments (i.e. items with low or no relevance) are not used in the current system, as negative boosting is not supported by Solr. As a result, using terms extracted from the set of low relevance items to restrict the query would possibly lead to the exclusion of other items that might be considered as relevant. Instead, to leverage negative feedback by users, the “exclude” feature of Solr queries was used that discards selected items (the ones that were marked as irrelevant by end users).

4 Improved Audience Analysis

Another important goal of our work during the second project period has been the development of tools that support the discovery of social media accounts that could be of relevance to the project topics and the improved understanding of the project social media audience, employing established social media metrics, as well as sophisticated social network analysis approaches. To this end, we first present a newly introduced approach for the discovery and ranking of relevant social media accounts based on automatic querying of several social media APIs and the subsequent classification of returned results into relevant and non-relevant (Section 4.1). Then, we proceed with the analysis of the STEP social media audience by employing a social network analysis approach based on community detection (Section 4.2). Finally, we resort to the facilities of social media platforms for measuring audience engagement (Section 4.3).

4.1 Relevant account discovery and ranking

Being able to discover social media accounts that are of relevance to STEP in terms of topics that they discuss could be of significant value both for generating awareness to the partners of the consortium about topics that are discussed among key stakeholders and for identifying potential targets of future dissemination and exploitation activities for the project (since several of the discovered accounts are relevant persons or organizations that are located in Europe and are active in the areas of interest for STEP). A challenge we faced in this effort was that dialogues on the STEP platform correspond to overly specific topics. To overcome this limitation, we had to consider more general topics that included the concepts of the dialogues (since from our preliminary experiments it became clear that querying social media APIs with very specific keywords returned very limited results). As a result, we created a list of general concepts in line with the ones presented in Section 3.1. The resulting list of general concepts comprises the subjects presented in Table 7.

Table 7: General concepts from STEP pilot dialogues

Concept	Details
Ecology	Endangered Species, Caretta-Caretta, Natura 2000, biodiversity, etc.
Climate Change	Climate Change
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
Eco - efficiency	Green lifestyle, green cities, sustainable power, energy conservation, etc.
Stray animals	Stray animals
Water protection	Wastewater treatment, marine pollution, water scarcity
Urban environment	Green transport, public spaces, parks, green infrastructure, etc.

The overall account discovery and classification methodology comprises several steps. The first two steps deal with the creation of a seed list of keywords related to each topic of interest and their use as query terms in the APIs of social media platforms. After a set of candidate accounts is generated in these steps, a filtering step takes place that aims at discarding accounts that are not relevant with a given concept despite having been retrieved with concept-related keywords (we observed this to be a common issue). To this end, classifiers are employed to classify accounts as relevant/irrelevant with each concept based on the text contained in the description field of the account profiles. To build the classifiers, we used a set of training accounts that were manually annotated as relevant/irrelevant. The output of this step is a set of accounts that are very likely to be relevant with the general concepts of Table 7. However, some of these accounts might be inactive for a long period and hence not useful for our purposes. Thus, an additional filtering step is applied to discard such accounts.

4.1.1 Keyword selection & querying social media APIs

The selection of appropriate keyword terms for querying the APIs of social media platforms is important for the overall effectiveness of account discovery as it determines the initial pool of candidate accounts. We carefully crafted a list of keywords for every concept. We chose a relatively small number of keywords with direct relevance for each concept in order to avoid a lot of noise in the initial list. Additionally, we chose only to focus on English keywords and English accounts because simple translation of keywords would lead to poor results.

Table 8: List of keywords for account retrieval for each general concept

Ecology	ecosystem, preservation, conservation, biodiversity, natura2000, natura2000day, european environment agency, ecological network, ecosystem, environment, ecology, eunature, wildlife, protected species, endangered species, caretta caretta, caretta caretta, turtleday, WorldTurtleDay
Eco-efficiency	energy conservation, clean energy, ecological footprint, energy consumption, renewable energy, sustainability, renewables, wind energy, alternative energy, gogreen, green, greener, green tips, ecotips, greenliving, ecoliving, ecogreen, ecofriendly, eco gardening , greencity, green city, eco life, greenlifestyle, green life style, greenhome, green home
Climate change	greenhouse gases, carbon dioxide, global warming, emissions, greenhouse effect, atmosphere, low-carbon, zero emissions, industrial emissions, air pollution, global environment, aerosol, acid rain, atmospheric emission, photochemical pollution, carbon footprint
Sustainable Development Goals	sdg, sdgs, sustainabledevelopmentgoals, developmentgoals, makepovertyhistory, genderequity, globalgoals, GlobalGoalsUN, ZeroHunger, UN4RefugeesMigrants, EATx, UNGA71, UNGA, Together2030, 2030NOW, UNPSF, LeaveNoOneBehind, 2030Agenda, sustainable development goals
Water protection	wastewater, wastewater treatment, wastedwater, drinking water, water treatment, water quality, water protection, groundwater protection, water scarcity, water reuse, clean water, water resource, sewage treatment, water contamination, marine pollution, water pollutant, coastal pollution, water conservation
Stray animals	stray, strays, straydogs, stray dogs, straycats, stray cats, straydog, stray dog, straycat, stray cat, strayanimal, stray animal, strayanimals, stray animals, SavetheStray, petadoption, pet adoption
Urban environment	urban farming, organic gardening, greenurbanlifestyle, green transport, green transportation, sustainable transport, sustainable transportation, ecological transportation, ecological transport, green building, green infrastructure, civil sustainability, green roofs, urban parks, city parks, public space, urban planning, viable city, viable cities, city accesibility, urban sprawl, sustainable urbanization, NewUrbanAgenda, TacticalUrbanism, Open Streets, UrbanAction, childinthecity, FutureOfPlaces, Habitat3

Having composed the list of search keywords, the next step is the retrieval of candidate accounts by querying the APIs of social media platforms, namely Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and Google+. Note that we refer to all returned objects as “accounts” even though they are different in nature (e.g. Twitter and Google+ users, Facebook pages, YouTube channels). The following paragraphs provide the details of how each API was queried. The collected results are then processed by the subsequent steps.

Twitter: We used the Twitter REST API⁸ to retrieve Twitter account information in JSON format using keywords. Specifically, we used the users/search⁹ endpoint that provides a simple, relevance-based search interface to public Twitter accounts. Documentation of the API also states that only the first 1,000 matching results are available per keyword query. Information about each retrieved account includes the account's name, location, language, description, number of followers, number of tweets, etc.

Facebook: To search for Facebook accounts, we used the Facebook Graph API¹⁰. This supports search over many public objects in the social graph with the search¹¹ endpoint. These objects include Users, Pages, Places, Events and other. Since User objects in Facebook typically represent actual persons and Graph API searches are based on object names, it would not make sense to search for User objects using the above keyword list. Facebook Pages, on the other hand, may represent organizations or causes and are therefore likely to contain concept-related terms as part of their names. Hence, we query the Graph API for Facebook pages containing the above keywords. Information about each retrieved Page includes name, location, language, description, number of likes, etc.

YouTube: The YouTube Data API¹² was used. There are different types of resources that can be retrieved using the API. To search for YouTube channels with relevant keywords, we used the search/list¹³ endpoint that returns a collection of search results that match the query parameters specified in the API request. By default, the set of results contains all matching video, channel and playlist resources but can be configured to return only YouTube channels. For each channel, information such as name, description, number of subscribers/videos/views, etc. is provided.

Google+: We attempt to discover concept-related accounts from Google+ by using the respective API¹⁴. Similarly to Facebook, Google+ contains various types of object (Users, Pages, etc). Unfortunately, the part of the API that provides access to Pages is not publicly available (special restrictions apply) and we therefore focused only on Google+ Users. To search for all Users with public profiles using relevant keywords, we used the People:search¹⁵ method. Information about each retrieved user includes name, description, number of followers (circledBy), number of +1s, etc.

4.1.2 Account classification

The previous steps of the account discovery pipeline resulted in a collection of accounts for each general concept that contain concept-related terms in their name and description field. However, we found that a significant portion of these accounts are not relevant to the input concept. Table 9 provides indicative examples of relevant and irrelevant accounts. As a result, it was considered necessary to create an additional mechanism for detecting and discarding irrelevant accounts. To this end, we trained a classifier for each concept to distinguish between relevant and irrelevant accounts based on the text in their description. To build these classifiers, for each concept we created a corresponding training set of examples that were manually labeled as relevant or irrelevant by reading the textual fields of the account profile (description). The text was preprocessed by applying stemming and stop-word removal and represented using a tf-idf bag-of-words representation. As classification algorithm, we used L2-regularized L2-loss Support Vector Machine (LibLinear implementation) with default parameters. Table 10 presents the resulting classifier performance (measured by Precision and Recall that were estimated using 10-fold cross-validation).

⁸ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs>

⁹ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/accounts-and-users/follow-search-get-users/api-reference/get-users-search>

¹⁰ <https://developers.facebook.com/docs/graph-api>

¹¹ <https://developers.facebook.com/docs/graph-api/using-graph-api/>

¹² <https://developers.google.com/youtube/v3/docs/>

¹³ <https://developers.google.com/youtube/v3/docs/search/list>

¹⁴ <https://developers.google.com/+web/api/rest/>

¹⁵ <https://developers.google.com/+web/api/rest/latest/people/search>

Table 9: Indicative examples of relevant and irrelevant accounts

Concept	Account name	Description	Label	Reason
Climate change	COP23	"COP23. Annual United Nations Climate Change Conference. Held in Bonn, Germany, 6-17 November 2017. Official account of incoming Fijian COP23 Presidency."	Relevant	Climate change relevant account
Climate change	Global Warming Hoax	Learning and tweeting about the great global warming hoax	Irrelevant	Global warming conspiracy theories
Water protection	Michael Dukes	Dr. Dukes specializes in water management and water quality of biological systems. He leads a research team investigating water conservation in urban systems.	Relevant	Water protection relevant account
Water protection	Jordan Valley Water	Wholesaler of drinking water to unincorporated Salt Lake County and 17 Member Agencies.	Irrelevant	Water wholesaler account

Table 10: Account classifier training set size and accuracy.

Classifier	#examples	#Relevant	#Irrelevant	Precision	Recall
Ecology	800	400	400	89.1%	88.6%
Climate Change	1000	500	500	92.3%	91.4%
Sustainable Development Goals	400	200	200	88.6%	87.4%
Eco - efficiency	1000	500	500	86.0%	87.1%
Stray animals	400	200	200	87.7%	89.1%
Water protection	500	250	250	84.9%	84.0%
Urban environment	500	250	250	88.9%	87.5%

4.1.3 Generating the final list of accounts

An additional step was performed to filter those of the discovered accounts that have been inactive (have not published new content) for a long period of time (we set this period to six months). To perform this step, additional API calls were required to retrieve the latest posts of each account and their timestamps. In the case of Facebook, for instance, the `/userid/feed`¹⁶ endpoint of the Graph API was queried to retrieve all public posts of the page along with their creation timestamps, while the same information is retrieved using the `Activities:list`¹⁷ method in the case of Google+. The final list of relevant accounts is available online¹⁸. By processing their description fields using a text-based location estimation module (Kordopatis-Zilos et al., 2017), we could also derive the geographical distribution of the accounts¹⁹. It is noteworthy that the discovered accounts are not restricted to the locations of the pilots but span the whole globe, exhibiting stronger presence in the US, UK, India and the BeNeLux. This is likely due to a number of characteristics of these locations, namely the increased adoption of social media, the large percentage of users posting in English, and the higher interest in topics related to environment and civic engagement.

¹⁶ <https://developers.facebook.com/docs/graph-api/reference/v2.10/page/feed>

¹⁷ <https://developers.google.com/+/web/api/rest/latest/activities/list>

¹⁸ <https://goo.gl/8MoqbG>

¹⁹ <https://goo.gl/mwzDei>

4.2 *STEP audience analysis*

Important insights regarding the audience of the STEP social media account can be derived by analysis of the structure of its network. As most social networks, the network of followers of the STEP Twitter account possesses community structure (Fortunato, 2010; Papadopoulos et al., 2012), i.e. the nodes of the network (followers) tend to be clustered into groups with dense connections internally and sparser connections across groups. Uncovering community structure could be valuable for a more in-depth understanding of the topics of interest, links, roles and dynamics of the network (e.g. information sharing within a community).

In this section, we present a methodology and analysis of the structure of the network of STEP's followers that led to the discovery of distinct communities of followers and of highly influential users in these communities. We also carried out a similar analysis on the structure of the networks that form around selected accounts that are relevant for the STEP Pilots. We believe that such an analysis is particularly useful for STEP's communication managers, and could help them better design and assess their dissemination and engagement strategies.

This methodology is not applicable to Facebook platform due to API limitations as we cannot retrieve information about which Facebook User or Page liked a particular Page.

4.2.1 *Follower graph construction*

Graph is a structure that is used to represent sets of objects that exhibit pairwise relations between them. Formally a graph is an ordered pair $G=(V,E)$ comprising a set of vertices or nodes V together with a set of edges E , which are 2-element subsets of V (i.e., an edge associates two vertices). In our case, the vertices of the graph correspond to Twitter accounts and the edges of the graph correspond to the followship relationships between pairs of accounts, i.e. the edges have directionality.

To build this type of graph, the necessary data is retrieved from the Twitter API. In particular, the followers/ids endpoint²⁰ was used, which returns a collection of user ids for every user following the specified user. The endpoint is first queried using the id of the initial account or accounts as input, returning the ids of the immediate followers of that account or accounts. Then, to retrieve the followers of initial account's followers, the same endpoint is used treating each of the returned accounts as input to a new query.

Note that the aforementioned data collection procedure takes a significant amount of time because the Twitter API allows only 60 requests per hour to the followers/ids endpoint. Also, each request retrieves up to 5,000 followers of a specified user. Retrieving more than 5,000 followers requires a corresponding number of requests. Due to this limitation, we retrieve up to a maximum of 5,000 followers per user. Moreover, to facilitate a more informative visualization of the graph, additional queries must be performed to retrieve the account names (e.g. @STEP_H2020) corresponding to the retrieved account ids (e.g. 3343978983). In particular, the users/lookup endpoint²¹ was used, which returns user objects for up to 100 users per request, as specified by comma-separated values passed to the user_id parameter. The Twitter API allows a significantly higher number of requests per hour to this endpoint (3600), thus making this part of the process less time-consuming.

²⁰<https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/accounts-and-users/follow-search-get-users/api-reference/get-followers-ids>

²¹<https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/accounts-and-users/follow-search-get-users/api-reference/get-users-lookup>

4.2.2 Community detection and visualization

To perform community detection in the graph of STEP followers, we used the Louvain algorithm (Blondel, Guillaume, Lambiotte, & Lefebvre, 2008). This is one of the most widely used algorithms and has been successfully applied to networks of many different types, including social networks sampled from Twitter (Grabowicz, Ramasco, Moro, Pujol, & Eguiluz, 2012) and LinkedIn (Haynes & Perisic, 2009). The method is a greedy optimizer of modularity, a measure of network structure that quantifies the quality of a community assignment by measuring how much denser the connections are within communities compared to what they would be in a random network.

The Louvain method works in two steps. In the first step, the method looks for "small" communities by optimizing modularity locally. In the second step, it aggregates nodes belonging to the same community and builds a new network where nodes represent communities. These steps are repeated iteratively until a maximum of modularity is attained and a hierarchy of communities is produced. Although the exact computational complexity of the method is not known, the method has been empirically demonstrated to run in time $O(n \log n)$ with most of the computational effort spent on the optimization at the first level.

Before applying the Louvain method on the followers graphs, we first removed leaf-nodes (i.e. Twitter accounts that are connected to only one other account) to simplify the graph and to facilitate a better (i.e. "cleaner") visual representation, i.e. a smaller (and denser) graph. We used the implementation offered by the Gephi²² open-source graph analysis and visualization software with default parameters. For the visualization of the graph, we used the Gephi software and the ForceAtlas2 (Jacomy, Venturini, Heymann, & Bastian, 2014) graph layout algorithm. Furthermore, nodes are colored according to their community assignment and their size is proportional to their edge degree (i.e. total number of incoming edges). By inspecting the most influential nodes (those with higher degree) of each community, we attempted to label the most coherent of the discovered communities.

4.2.3 Communities around STEP Twitter account

We first present the results of community detection and analysis on the network of followers of the STEP Twitter account (@STEP_H2020). To create the follower graph, we followed the process of subsection 4.2.1 using the STEP account (@STEP_H2020) as input. The resulting network, when this procedure was applied in mid-October, comprised 263,228 follow relationships (graph edges) between 227,925 distinct accounts (graph vertices), 233 of which were immediate followers of STEP account. We then used the users/lookup endpoint to retrieve Twitter information about these distinct accounts.

To simplify the graph and to facilitate a better visual inspection, we first removed leaf-nodes. This led to a smaller (and denser) graph of 22,321 nodes and 57,598 edges. When the Louvain algorithm was applied on this graph, 10 different communities were discovered (0.563 modularity score).

Figure 8 shows a visualization of the graph. By inspecting the most influential nodes (those with higher degree) per community, the following seven coherent communities of Twitter accounts were identified (labeled in the figure): 1) Greek accounts, 2) European accounts, projects – innovation A, 3) European accounts, projects – innovation B, 4) Sustainable Development Goals, 5) Youth job opportunities, 6) Entrepreneurs–Media influencers 7) Valdemoro accounts. The @STEP_H2020 account is located at the center of the graph and was assigned by the algorithm to the Greek accounts community. We have also created a very similar web-based view of this graph to facilitate the interactive exploration of the STEP two-hop neighborhood. This web-view is available online²³.

²² <https://gephi.org/>

²³ http://smmt.step.green/ui/STEP_Network/: The implementation is based on the linkurio.us WebGL library.

Figure 8: Visualization of different communities in the STEP followers of followers network

As an example, Figure 9 zooms into the Valdemoro accounts community, allowing a more detailed inspection of its structure and the most influential users and connections between them. Similar zoomed-in views have been generated for all the discovered communities and are provided in Appendix I.

Figure 9: The Valdemoro accounts community of the STEP followers of followers network

4.2.3.1 Influential Twitter users in STEP network

Using information from the STEP followers' network graph, we located the most influential accounts. To do this, we sorted nodes based on their number of incoming edges. To simplify the analysis, we used the simpler graph described above, which has all leaf-nodes removed. Table 11 lists a subset of the identified influential users (the full list is provided in Appendix I). Notice that due to the nature of the graph, all identified users are followers of the STEP account. Although discovering influential users out of the existing follower base of STEP is useful for tailoring the social media strategy of the project, we were further interested in relevant influential accounts that do not follow the STEP account. This effort is described in the next paragraph.

Table 11: Influential accounts based of their incoming degree

Username	Link	In- degree
@gazzema	Communication Adviser @EU_Commission @Energy4Europe @ristori20•#Energy #H2020 #SmartCities #SETPlan #Tw4SE #SETPlan17 Coaching staff https://t.co/e4QMyze4w7	2808
@stracma	Head of Unit New #energy techs & #innovation @EU_Commission @Energy4Europe #EnergySystem #SmartCities #SmartGrid #EnergyStorage #SETPlan #SETPlan17 RT#endors	2617
@HansLak	Accelerating the #GlobalGoals #SDGs #2030now Catalyst for social #innovation and #transformation @PostNormalEra Let's connect on LinkedIn	1824
@EUSciComm	Promoting #EUSciComm news and views and #womeninSTEM. Focused on the EU funding programme #Horizon2020 (#H2020), not EU affiliated, managed by @garybridgeman.	1663
@EU_eGov	European Commission, CONNECT 'eGovernment & Trust', wking on Digital Public Services and ICT-enabled Public Sector Innovation (RT not endorsement)	1632
@energycoin	Welcome! We build the EnergyCoin \$ENRG community based value platform @efc4u #energyefficiency #renewables #smartgrid #p2p #energystorage maintained @insidestat	1488
@EU_GreenCapital	The official European Green Capital and European Green Leaf Award. Our aim is to improve Europe's urban environment. Tweets by EGCA and EGLA Secretariat.	1299
@EU_opendata	Official account of the EU Open Data Portal (https://t.co/S55H1P74hd) and of #EUOpenData policy. Co-organising #EUdatathon2017 with @EU2017EE	1281
@TeachSDGs	A global movement of teachers pledging to #TeachSDGs; a Task Force of volunteers partnered with the UN to serve @TheGlobalGoals & @TheWorldsLesson. Join us.	1180
@Impakterdotcom	Magazine about Culture, Style, Society with articles by our Team & Global Leaders from UnitedNations, Institutes, NGO. Focus: #SDGs #Tech #Health #Style ...	1176
@EU_H2020	The official account for the EU's #H2020 research and innovation programme. Managed by DG Research & Innovation. Follow Commissioner @moedas too.	1167
@wellbelove	Frequent smiler, marketer, professionally qualified social media expert, presenter, speaker, geek, Lambeth councillor, former Mayor and Parliament candidate.	1164
@Pieterschie	Solving #Young #Jobs Puzzle Chief Exec.MD Werkcenter Int.Chairman @LVV_FF #EU & #Employment Expert Multiple Award Winner/drs.Politicologie MA(Leiden University)	1088
@MarcGuberti	19 Year Old Entrepreneur, Author, Blogger, Digital Marketing Expert, Speaker, Instructor @HootSuite Ambassador, Runner, Dog Lover, Red Sox fan	1067

4.2.3.2 Influential Twitter users that do not follow STEP

To find influential users that appear in the graph but do not follow the STEP account, we needed information about the number of followers of these users. This information was already retrieved when we queried the user/lookup endpoint. Due to the fact that a large amount of these users may be irrelevant with STEP topics, we make the following assumption regarding relevance: the relevance of an account for STEP is highly dependent on the number of STEP followers that this account follows. With this in mind, we first filtered accounts with less than 1000 followers and then also filtered accounts that followed less than 10 STEP followers. The resulting list in Table 12 is a subset of the 55 accounts that were retrieved with this process (the full list is available in Appendix I). This list can serve as a valuable resource for STEP communication managers, who could directly approach these accounts with the goal of engaging them in the STEP outcomes.

Table 12: Most influential users that do not follow STEP account

Username	Link	Followers	#STEP followers
@6BillionPeople	Looking for the best artist in the world! All Genres, All Artist. The #Musicindustrycontest ends Oct 27th 2017! submit your best two songs. Click link in my bio	4,460,787	16
@DigitalTrendsDigitalTrends	Tech for the way we live. Facebook & Instagram: @DigitalTrends	1,924,348	11
DennisKoutoudis	Entrepreneur Founder & CEO of https://t.co/2ene73iUD3 Influential LinkedIn Expert International Keynote Speaker Author	1,782,972	10
@johnrampton	Entrepreneur and connector. Founder of @Due. I blog about my successes and epic failures for @Entrepreneur @TechCrunch and @Mashable #fintech	1,538,495	11
@AskAaronLee	Regional Manager APAC @agorapulse. Trying to perfect the art of cappuccino. Introvert with awesome hair. https://t.co/PZNF06OICy ✉️ hi@askaaronlee.com	1,118,753	13
@drjoyce_knudsen	#SeniorFashionista Creator Global Style System #ImpressionManagement Podcast Radio PsychToday Women's Day Glamour #TrueGiver https://t.co/Xk2JiDXfZY	1,117,163	13
@StartupPro	Veteran startup mentor, executive, blogger, author, tech professional, and Angel investor. Published on Forbes, Entrepreneur, Inc, Huffington Post, and others.	1,024,491	11
@LeadToday	Improving the Sales Profession, Developing the Next Generation of Leaders, Not selling a thing on Twitter, only giving back.	994,978	14
@annemariayrity	Anne-Maria Yrity™ Social Media Influencer Thought Leader I am a leader: I (un)follow back. #IFB. FREE leadership tips @leadingwithpassion dot org	660,008	15
@MikeSchiermer	Frugal Entrepreneur Digital Marketing Manager Investor Top 100 Social Media Influencer Author of The \$10 Digital Media Startup: https://t.co/6QzPM0vs0U	233,693	14
@RNFinfo	Ciudadano Citizen, Former Science and Technology Communications Advisor	179,362	10
@Esri	Esri users create maps that run the world. #ArcGIS an open platform for #GIS #3D #Imagery #Apps #IoT #Cities #BigData #Geodesign #TheScienceofWhere	153,249	10
@evankirstel	#Influencer #ThoughtLeader Helping #B2B clients w #SocialMediaMarketing in #Enterprise #IoT #Telecom #Security #Cloud and #DigitalHealth at https://t.co/Y9NQcCGUp7	152,489	11

4.2.4 Communities around STEP pilots

For discovering communities in the network of followers of the STEP pilot accounts, we first manually chose a small number of accounts from every pilot community in STEP project. Due to Twitter API limitations, we avoided accounts with more than 1000 followers, as they would result in very large and potentially “noisy” networks (i.e. networks without clear focus on environmental issues). In cases where this was not possible, we retrieved up to 1000 followers of each seed account. The selected seed pilot accounts are presented in Table 13.

Table 13: Seed accounts for STEP Pilot graph

name	username	description	followers
Step Locride H2020	steplocride		19
Fai_Locride_Piana	FaiLocride Piana	Fondo Ambiente Italiano, fondazione nazionale senza scopo di lucro, dal 1975 con un obiettivo: agire per la salvaguardia...	49
Legambiente Calabria	LegambienteCal		566
STEP-Crete	STEP_Crete	Πιλοτική εφαρμογή από την Περιφέρεια Κρήτης του Ευρωπαϊκού προγράμματος Horizon2020 STEP	12
Πανεπιστήμιο Κρήτης	UOC_gr	Επίσημος λογαριασμός του Πανεπιστημίου Κρήτης στο Twitter. The official Twitter account of the University of...	212
LIFE N2000ValueCrete	Natura200Ovalue	Ανάδειξη της αξίας των υπηρεσιών οικοσυστημάτων σε περιοχές NATURA 2000 στη Κρήτη / Raising awareness on...	248
NHMC	nhmcrete		139
Ayto de Valdemoro	Ayto_Valdemoro		2896
Guillermo Gross	guillermo_gross	Este es mi perfil personal. Comprometido con la idea del progreso a base de infinitos cambios infinitesimales.	1462
Alcalde de Valdemoro	sera_alcalde	Este es mi Twitter oficial como Alcalde de Valdemoro. Trabajo por hacer mi ciudad más justa, sostenible y con mayor ...	480
Ajuntament de Mollet	ajmollet	Twitter oficial de l'Ajuntament de Mollet del Vallès. Actualitat, agenda d'activitats i informacions de servei	3810
ECOMOLLET	EcoMollet	Associació d'ecoconsum de #Mollet del Vallès. Per comprar fruita i verdura #ecològica a bon preu, de #proximitat i ...	164
Joventut Mollet	joventutmollet	Tota la informació d'activitats del Servei de Joventut de l'Ajuntament de Mollet del Vallès.	944
Draxis Environmental	DraxisEnv	Environmental Studies and research - Environmental Software – GIS	114
Pantelis Pekakis	PPekakis	Environmental Engineer at @DraxisEnv	20
Resilient Thess	ResilienceThess	Thessaloniki is part of the 100ResilientCities initiative pioneered by the Rockefeller Foundation.	292
Lina Liakou	linaliakou	Regional Director for Europe and the Middle East for @100ResCities, former Deputy Mayor and Chief Resilience ...	709
STEP Projesi Hatay	stepgreenhatay	STEP GREEN Projesi Resmi Twitter Hesabıdır. https://t.co/mURw9Q6As4 https://t.co/6ngS18GU8S	733
Hatay Vatan	hatayvatancom	Hatay Vatan Gazetesi Resmi Twitter Hesabıdır.	152
GençTema Hatay	genctema_hatay	TEMA Gönüllüsü olmak ve bizimle irtibata geçmek için; genctemahatay@gmail.com	214
#YouthDay ActOn2250	Youth4SDG	A global network of Young men and women who are playing an active role in the implementation of Sustainable...	1088
#YouthSDGs	YouthSDGs	We are 1.8 billion youth ready to implement & monitor the Global Goals. #youthSDGs to share your youth & SDGs stories.	6442
UN Climate Change	UNFCCC	Official twitter account of UN Climate Change. Also in French (@CCNUCC), Spanish (@CMNUCC) & German (@UNKlima). ...	434265
COP23	COP23	COP23. Annual United Nations Climate Change Conference. ...	49760

To create the follower graph, we followed the process of subsection 4.2.1. Then, we aggregated the resulting relations of each STEP pilot account to a universal network. The size of the universal network is 6,514,944 followship relationships (graph edges) and 4,054,130 accounts (graph vertices). We used the users/lookup endpoint to retrieve Twitter information about these distinct accounts. To be able to process the graph we removed all nodes with degree 2 or smaller. This led to a smaller (and denser) graph of 385,071 nodes and 2,401,911 edges. When the Louvain algorithm was applied on this graph, 10 different communities were discovered (0.682 modularity score).

There are 6 major and 4 small communities among the discovered ones. To name the communities we inspected the nodes with the highest degree per community. Another way to identify the discovered communities is by inspecting the language or location of the Twitter accounts. Table 14 shows the top 5 locations per discovered community.

Table 14: Top 5 account locations in each of the major discovered communities

Community 1	Community 2	Community 3	Community 4	Community 5	Community 6
Italia 1016	Madrid 1462	London, England 1879	Greece 3873	Barcelona 5286	İstanbul, Türkiye 681
Roma 990	España 1030	London 1851	Athens 2564	Catalunya 1852	Turkey 346
Italy 946	Madrid, Comunidad de Madrid 765	Washington, DC 1498	Athens, Greece 2419	Barcelona, Spain 1531	Türkiye 250
Milano 558	Spain 485	United States 1450	Thessaloniki, Greece 1142	España 1481	Ankara, Türkiye 232
Rome, Lazio 352	Madrid, España 257	New York, NY 1437	Thessaloniki 974	Spain 902	Ankara 200

After inspection, the following six coherent communities of Twitter accounts were identified (labeled in Figure 10): 1) Italian (Locride) accounts, 2) Spanish (Valdemoro) accounts, 3) Greek (Thessaloniki – Crete) accounts, 4) Catalan (Mollet) accounts, 5) Turkish (Hatay) accounts, 6) SDGs – Climate Change accounts. Similar to the previous graph, we created a web-based view of this graph to facilitate the interactive exploration of the STEP two-hop neighborhood. To deal with the large amount of users we only incorporated accounts with overall degree equal or larger than 10. This web-view is available online²⁴.

Table 15 provides a better sense about the size of the communities. We observe that SDGs and Climate Change is the largest community in the network and Turkish (Hatay) accounts the smallest. Table 16 shows the relationship between the discovered communities in terms of number of follow relations between their accounts. As expected, Catalan and Spanish communities have numerous such relations between them, while the same is also true for the SDG and Climate Change community and the Greek (Thessaloniki-Crete) one. Figure 11 depicts the relationship between the discovered communities in a simplified graph.

²⁴ http://smtt.step.green/ui/STEP_Pilots/

Figure 10: STEP Pilot network communities

Table 15: The size of each discovered community.

Community name	Number of nodes
Italian (Locride) accounts	33,310
Spanish (Valdemoro) accounts	27,526
SDGs and Climate Change accounts	143,698
Greek (Thessaloniki-Crete) accounts	71,936
Catalan (Mollet) accounts	69,710
Turkish (Hatay) accounts	27,264

Table 16: Follow connections between STEP Pilot communities

	Italian (Locride)	Spanish (Valdemoro)	SDGs and Climate Change	Greek (Thessaloniki-Crete)	Catalan (Mollet)
Italian (Locride)	231,157	186	9,071	2,046	1,313
Spanish (Valdemoro)	311	168,623	2,969	623	17,646
SDGs and Climate Change	10,690	2,256	738,267	22,981	13,366
Greek (Thessaloniki-Crete)	980	217	11,768	482,347	865
Catalan (Mollet)	1,348	17,038	13,822	2,042	402,260

Figure 11: Follow connections between STEP Pilot communities. Bigger circles represent bigger communities. Also, bold edges mean stronger connections between communities

Following the analysis of the structure of the identified communities, we try to characterize the discovered communities based on the content their accounts post. Also, we try to locate relevant users and provide some further analysis.

For this task, we collect 100 most recent tweets (including retweets) from the top 10,000 most influential users (those with the highest degree) per community. In total, we collected tweets from 60,000 users from the STEP Pilot graph. This process led to a collection of 4,422,468 tweets, which was collected using the statuses/user_timeline²⁵ endpoint. We then applied the post classifier presented in section 3.1. We selected the proper language classifier based on the language field²⁶ of each tweet. We removed tweets with language other than English, Italian, Spanish, Catalan, Greek or Turkish.

Table 17 presents the classification results. We notice that the number of relevant tweets is relatively low in comparison with the total number of tweets per community. On the other hand, the engagement of users is relatively high as large amount of users per community posted or retweeted at least one relevant tweet.

Table 17: Tweet classification results

Community name	Number of Tweets	Relevant Tweets	Relevant Tweet ratio	Number of users with >1 relevant tweet	User engagement ratio
Italian (Locride)	797,983	18,027	0.022	5,346	0.53
Spanish (Valdemoro)	858,532	8,117	0.009	4,274	0.43
SDGs and Climate Change	801,594	55,227	0.068	7,569	0.76
Greek (Thessaloniki-Crete)	769,619	9,940	0.129	4,296	0.43
Catalan (Mollet)	634,305	8,184	0.129	3,035	0.30
Turkish (Hatay)	660,435	10,960	0.165	3,760	0.38

²⁵ https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/tweets/timelines/api-reference/get-statuses-user_timeline

²⁶ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/tweets/data-dictionary/overview/tweet-object>

Having this information we can now discover users from the communities that are frequent content creators on relevant topics. Table 18 lists a subset of the users with the most relevant tweets out of their 100 most recent tweets (the full list is presented in Appendix I). Table 44 and Table 45 in Appendix I list the top 5 users in terms of related tweets per community and per concept respectively.

Table 18: Top 50 users based on the number of relevant tweets they posted

Username	Rel. Tweets (%)	Community	Description
@apruxtweet	87	Italian (Locride)	Communication strategist, press officer and journalist. #green #sustainability #smartcity #sostenibilità #comunicazione Amo il buon cibo, ...
@globalyouth	84	SDGs and Climate Change	Global Youth Action Network: Youth. Participation. Collaboration. Action
@EnergyBoom	82	SDGs and Climate Change	Tweeting the latest renewable energy, environment and clean tech news!
@CarbonXprint	79	SDGs and Climate Change	Translating concern for climate change into measurable and profitable action. Ask us how!
@FreeReporter	77	Italian (Locride)	Collaborative #journalism on #environment, #sustainability and #conflicts / #Giornalismo collaborativo su #ambiente, #sostenibilita e #conflitti
@reducepollution	73	SDGs and Climate Change	Official twitter account of the Pollution news and environmental information website http://t.co/lzISrPrThK
@FreeSolarFarms	73	SDGs and Climate Change	Renewable Energy, Solar Power, Solar Energy, Solar Panels, PV, EV, Solar Farms, Wind Power, Photovoltaics, Internet, SEO, Fishing, Comedy, Live Music, Live Dead
@Climate_Science	72	Italian (Locride)	Be the change – create a green economy by following the latest independent news about climate science & the UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).
@GreenDiwali2017	71	SDGs and Climate Change	Joining hands from this Diwali to clean up the once most beautiful parts of the city- Lakes 9717064159/8585952994
@GIN_GROUP	71	Italian (Locride)	GIN GROUP e' distribuzione e rivendita di prodotti per Energia alternativa, Risparmio Energetico, Edilizia Innovativa. Richieste a network@gingroup.it
@ENERGIALIMPIA21	69	Catalan (Mollet)	SIGUENOS Y TE SEGUIMOS
@phervas	67	Spanish (Valdemoro)	Lo mejor está por llegar...
@BayshoreRecycle	67	Turkish (Hatay)	Full service & award winning recycling facility in NJ. Environmental leader and WBE in NJ and NY. Go green with us!
@TreesUganda	65	SDGs and Climate Change	Planting Trees in Uganda UG Giving mother nature 🌱 🌱 🌱 a fighting chance against Destruction Together 🤝 we can revive mother nature's 🌱 🌱 🌱 heartbeat

To gain a better understanding about the concept of interest for each community, we also computed the number of tweets that are posted for each topic per community. In Table 19 we can observe that ecology and climate change are the most discussed concepts in every community except the Italian, where eco-efficiency is one of the most interesting topics.

Table 19: Top 5 most discussed concepts per community

Community	Concept	Associated tweets
Italian (Locride)	Eco-efficiency	5,426
	Ecology	4,893
	Climate change	4,156
	Waste	2,177
	Land degradation	1,984
Spanish (Valdemoro)	Ecology	3,413
	Climate change	1,397
	Environmental policy	966
	Eco efficiency	917
	Land degradation	652
SDGs and Climate Change	Climate change	16,677
	Ecology	14,299
	Eco-efficiency	9,162
	Environmental policy	4,357
	Land degradation	3,953
Greek (Thessaloniki-Crete)	Ecology	3,228
	Climate change	2,275
	Eco-efficiency	1,367
	Land degradation	1,280
	Environmental policy	725
Catalan (Mollet)	Ecology	2,689
	Climate change	1,787
	Eco-efficiency	1,280
	Environmental policy	661
	Land degradation	651
Turkish (Hatay)	Ecology	3,181
	Climate change	2,581
	Eco-efficiency	1,592
	Land degradation	1,385
	Water protection	743

4.3 Engagement measurements

As a final step towards the analysis of the STEP audience, we resorted to the native mechanisms and metrics provided by social media platforms: a) Facebook Insights and b) Twitter analytics. Having a deep understanding of the people that follow, interact and engage with STEP, is critical for municipalities to drive content creation, develop services catered for the specific needs, behaviors, and concerns of different groups, follow up, and anything that relates to acquiring and retaining the interest of citizens.

According to Facebook Insights, 55% of the people that like STEP are women and 45% men. Millennials (in particular aging from 25 to 34) represent the most dominant age group (41%), of which 25% corresponds to women and the remaining 16% to men. People reached, come (mainly) from Greece, Turkey, Italy,

Belgium, UK and Spain a fact that makes sense considering the pilots of the project. On Twitter, 57% men and 43% women comprise the audience. Countrywise, similar to Facebook, Twitter followers come mainly from Greece, Spain, United Kingdom, Italy and Belgium.

Facebook's Audience Insights suggest that people who like STEP are usually educated (college graduates), young (25-34), interested in sports events (e.g., Thessaloniki Half Marathon), Community Organizations (No Hate Speech Movement). Moreover, they are also involved in youth organizations (United Societies of Balkans, Eurodesk), Environmental Consultants (European Environment Agency), NGOs (YEE, Youth for Exchange and Understanding International) and Cultural Events (TEDx, Thessalonki International Film Festival). The vast majority of Twitter followers on the other hand (72%), are interested in Business and news, Tech news (71%), Politics and current events (70%) and science news (68%). Such differences in audience analytics are not rare across different social media platforms. However, they are really important for campaign organizers to create, deliver and tailor their content so that they can capture the pulse of each audience in each social media platform of interest. As it appears, different types of content would appeal to Facebook users as opposed to Twitter followers. In order to get a full understanding of what makes the best followers/citizens tick, it is critical to develop detailed personas for an initiative so as to map out and disseminate highly targeted messaging.

Another useful insight that Facebook provides is the fact that personas in this audience are very likely to access the platform both via desktop and mobile (based on user activity and environmental data). In particular, last month statistics show that 60% of the selected audience accessed Facebook via Android devices, 20% via iPhone and 20% via Desktop. This further indicates that in order to reach citizens, public authorities for environmental causes and similar initiatives, public servants should deliver responsive content that can be easily consumed across all devices.

In addition, page insights reveal that STEP fans are online and active throughout the week (no significant day-to-day variance is observed) mainly from 11am to 11pm. Average organic reach is slightly higher for "Link" type posts followed by "Photo" type posts whereas in terms of average engagement "Photo" type posts come first. Therefore a successful campaign to engage young people in the environmental decision making of local authorities should include engaging multimedia (for example images in the form of Canvas in the case of Facebook advertisements) taking place throughout the week late morning through almost mid-night.

Overall, the STEP Facebook page created 212 posts (120 photos, 22 videos, 64 links, 4 statuses and 2 events) that engaged 469 reactors and 5 commenters. STEP brought about 1.5K reactions in total (average 7 per post) and 350 shares (again in total). To dig deeper into the reach, engagement and audience grouping, Figure 12 presents a snapshot from the "Reach" section of Facebook's Insights²⁷ page where a trend line of post reach is provided, distinguishing between organic and paid (i.e. the result of a post promotion campaign) reach, while Figure 13 shows a snapshot from the "People" section of Facebook's Insights pages where aggregated demographic data about the people who have seen content associated with STEP's Facebook page are provided (i.e. age/gender grouping, top countries, cities and languages).

²⁷ <https://www.facebook.com/business/news/audience-insights>

Figure 12: Post reach of STEP account from Facebook insights page

Figure 13: Audience demographics of STEP account from Facebook insights page

In the same way Twitter also provides analytics²⁸ about content reach and Audience demographics. Figure 14 and Figure 15 depict the reach of STEP's tweets and audience demographics respectively.

²⁸ <https://business.twitter.com/en/analytics.html>

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

Figure 14: Tweet reach of STEP account from Twitter analytics page

Figure 15: Audience demographics of STEP account from Twitter analytics page

To get more insights about the number of users that STEP posts can reach, we calculate the maximum reach of the STEP account (how many users can see a tweet if all followers retweet it) and we try to detect the most active followers and their corresponding communities. The STEP Twitter account has 233 followers. From the previous section, it was found that 227,925 accounts follow these 233 users. Therefore, if every STEP follower retweeted its tweets, these could potentially reach 227,925 accounts. In practice, however, only a small number of followers retweet posts (this is a general observation and not particular for STEP account). To quantify the actual retweeting activity around STEP, we query the statuses/user_timeline endpoint²⁹, which returns a collection of the most recent Tweets posted by a certain user (@STEP_H2020 in our case). At the end of October 2017, the STEP account timeline had 210

²⁹ https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/tweets/timelines/api-reference/get-statuses-user_timeline

tweets, 69 of which were retweeted tweets from other accounts and 141 were original tweets. Furthermore, we queried the statuses/retweets/:id³⁰ endpoint, which returns a collection of the 100 most recent retweets of the Tweet specified by the id parameter, and used the ids of the above 141 tweets. Results showed that 50% of STEP account tweets are retweeted by at least one account. Also, 72 accounts have retweeted at least one tweet of the STEP account. Table 20 presents the top 15 accounts in terms of number of retweeting the tweets of the STEP account. Regularly monitoring this list can help communication managers identify the type of content that is mostly appealing to certain followers so that they can tune their future posting activity.

Table 20: Top 15 retweeters of STEP account

Username	Retweets	Community
PPekakis	16	Greekaccounts
YEEorganisation	9	SustainableDevelopmentGoals
EU_eGov	8	Europeanprojects – Innovation A
bb5abd9436d9421	6	Valdemoroaccounts
scientix_eu	4	Europeanprojects – Innovation A
STEP_Crete	4	Greekaccounts
TwittterWizard	3	Entrepreneurs - mediainfluencers
empatia_project	3	Europeanprojects – Innovation A
IPavlou	3	Greekaccounts
kompats	3	Greekaccounts
stepgreenhatay	2	Entrepreneurs - mediainfluencers
PaulaJForbes	2	Youthjobopportunities
dipsot	2	Greekaccounts
SergioParra85	2	Valdemoroaccounts
DraxisEnv	2	Greekaccounts
sympap	2	Greekaccounts

In a further analysis, to find the most actively retweeting communities, we calculate for each community the number of accounts that retweet STEP tweets and the number of retweets. Results for the most active communities are presented in Table 21. According to it, communities comprising Greek accounts, European projects – Innovation 1 and Sustainable Development Goals are the three most active in terms of spreading the STEP posts.

Table 21: Most active communities based on the number of retweeter

Community	Accounts retweeted	Retweets
Greek Accounts	11	36
European Projects – Innovation A	8	20
Sustainable development Goals	8	16
European Projects – Innovation B	4	4
Other	4	4
Valdemoro Accounts	3	9
Entrepreneurs - Media Influencers	2	5
Youth Job Opportunities	1	2

The final part of our analysis is based on the analysis of the distribution of retweets for STEP posts and their relation with the actual reach they achieve on the STEP follower network. It appears that the majority of

³⁰ <https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/tweets/post-and-engage/api-reference/get-statuses-retweets-id>

STEP posts receive zero or one retweet, while there are only few posts that were retweeted more times. However, analysis of the number of retweets on its own does not paint the whole picture. For that reason, we made use of the STEP follower graph in order to compute the maximum reach for each post. This was done by counting the total number of nodes on the network that could potentially be exposed to the posts. This is equal to the union of the neighborhoods (sets of neighboring nodes) of the STEP account and of all accounts that retweeted the post. Compared to the number of retweets, this is a much more representative measure of the audience size for STEP, since each time an account retweets a post, all its followers may potentially see it. Figure 16 provides an insightful view into the reach of STEP posts in the form of a scatter plot of the reach for each post (each post corresponds to a dot) in relation to the number of retweets that it achieved (x axis). Based on this, one may broadly categorize STEP posts in three groups:

- *Normal (blue dots – bottom left part):* These are posts that achieve the “expected” reach given the number of retweets. They exhibit a roughly linear relation between reach and number of retweets.
- *High performers (green dots-top part):* These are posts that exhibit high reach even though their numbers of retweets are in the same order of magnitude as the ones achieved by Normal posts.
- *Low-reach (red dots):* These are posts that only achieve low or moderate reach even though their numbers of retweets are higher than the ones of the Normal or even the High Performers.

Figure 16: Retweet and reach analysis of 141 STEP posts. Scatter plot of posts’ reach on the STEP follower graph versus their retweets.

5 User Interface Improvements

After a period in which pilots had a continuous interaction with the SMMT, they provided valuable feedback for potential improvements and extensions of the tool. Taking into account the proposed suggestions, the User Interface was refined with the goal of achieving better usability and increased usefulness. Improvements were applied not only to the already presented features (see Section 5.2 and 5.3) but also a new design (see Section 5.1) was implemented to facilitate the usage of the tool by pilot partners.

5.1 Redesign of pilots user interface

Despite its merits, end users (PA officers) with little or no technical knowledge and experience reported that the initial version of the SMMT was too complicated at some points and required effort and expertise to find the desired information. To this end, we redesigned the User Interface, offering a dedicated entry point for each pilot, and presenting all information in a more intuitive and accessible way, with the goal of helping pilot users gain more control and insights over their collections.

A new dedicated dashboard page is now available³¹, containing one collection for every active dialogue that has been created by the pilot, thus following the same structure as the main STEP platform. The dashboard consists of a number of widgets that are illustrated in the following figures.

The first widget (Figure 17) depicts a set of four summary metrics. Each of them represents an indicator of the popularity and diffusion for the given dialogue. The four metrics correspond to the total number of:

- Posts made (top left)
- Users Talking (top right)
- Users Reached (bottom left)
- Endorsements (bottom right)

Figure 17: Stats Widget

³¹ The page is available on: <http://smtt.step.green/ui/specified/>

Top contributing users are represented in the “users” widget (Figure 18). This widget is divided in two tabs, “Active” and “Influencers”. When the first tab is active, social media users who have published the most content relevant to the dialogue are shown. On the other hand, when the tab “Influencers” is active, key accounts (see section 4.1) for the dialogue are displayed. Along with the avatar and total number of posts, the widget displays the username, social platform and link to their profile for each account when hovering on the desired user.

Figure 18: Users Widget

The number of posts over time is visualized in a timeline widget (Figure 19). By hovering on a peak, users can see the absolute number of posts in that particular day.

Figure 19: Timeline Widget

The “Posts” widget (Figure 20) contains the most shared posts along with all the information that comes with them, including username, link and avatar of the author, text, publication time, social platform, link with the source and number of shares. Posts are presented with a carousel slideshow but there is also the ability to navigate by clicking on the left and right arrows on the side.

Figure 20: Posts Widget

The most relevant articles collected from the monitored RSS feeds are displayed in Figure 21. As in the previous widget, additional useful information comes along with the article, including a thumbnail of the website where the article comes from, the title and a small part of the article, the link to the article and the source. Through pagination all available articles can be viewed.

Figure 21: Articles Widget

The exact amount of contribution of each monitored social network, expressed in terms of percentage of posts is illustrated in the “platforms” widget (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Platforms Widgets

The “Tags” widget (Figure 23) presents the most frequent appearing entities, among the posts of the collection. Entities are divided in three main frequency categories (often occasionally, seldom) based on the number of their appearances, and in three types (person, tag, location). These types are obtained by using Stanford NER library³² on the textual content of the posts in the collection. The size of the circle reflects the frequency of appearance, with a bigger radius indicating more appearances. The type of the entity is represented by the color of the circle, with the correspondence shown in the legend of the graph. By hovering on a particular circle the absolute number of appearances is revealed.

Figure 23: Tags Widget

³² <https://nlp.stanford.edu/software/CRF-NER.shtml>

The result of posts classification, described in section 3.1, is pictured in the “Concepts” widget (Figure 24). The main circle contains the name of the collection and around it the detected concept of interest are depicted. Each circle represents a different class and its size declares the percentage of posts inside the collection that are classified with this class. Size and percentage correspondence are explained in the legend of the graph.

Figure 24: Concepts Widget

The exact location (latitude, longitude) from each post is displayed in the “Map” widget (Figure 25). Zoom in/out and pan functionalities are provided. The color of hexagons represents the number of posts coming from that location, with colors closer to red indicating high activity of posts and colors closer to green a lower one. Hovering on a hexagon reveals the absolute number of posts in a tooltip.

Figure 25: Map Widget

An entire view of the redesigned User Interface is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Overview of the Pilot Specific User Interface.

5.2 Improved user controls

The fact that some keywords are used in multiple contexts and have different senses was found to lead in some cases to noisy content. As a result, there is a risk that valuable information is masked by a large amount of irrelevant posts. To support better and more focused content collection, in the updated version of the SMMT, end users can provide a more restricted selection of input using new query facilities (section 5.2.1) or evaluate, filter and redefine the already collected (section 5.2.2).

5.2.1 New query facilities

In addition to expressions that consist of sets of input keywords, the end user can now create logical expressions (Figure 27), using the logical operators AND, OR, NOT and keywords to provide more specific content collection rules (e.g. exclude certain keywords from the collection). Drag-and-drop functionality is provided to arrange the operators and keywords, and the use of parenthesis enables end users to define the priority of individual logical expressions. After creation, logical expressions are checked by the SMMT and if found valid, they are added to the collection. Only posts that satisfy the expression(s) are collected.

Figure 27: Widget to support the insertion of logical expressions to define a collection

Beside the keywords and users accounts that can be used to define a collection, in the updated version of SMMT, it is also possible to define collections by geolocation: The end user can define areas (as polygons) on the map that correspond to the desired location (Figure 28). To determine a polygon the user can type a location to the input box and select one of the matching values from the dropdown menu, offered by Google Maps Place Autocomplete API³³. A rectangular box is then placed around the center of the location selected by the user. Polygons can also be designed directly on the map by the end user, by selecting points as peaks of polygon and matching the location of the first point with the last to complete the loop. All polygons are editable to expand or minimize the covered area, can be dragged and deleted. Once activated, every geolocated post with coordinates inside one of the polygons will be collected.

Figure 28: Widget for specifying the target geo-location for a collection

³³ <https://developers.google.com/maps/documentation/javascript/examples/places-autocomplete>

5.2.2 Content scoring and filtering

Content can be evaluated and filtered by the end user towards the relevance of it, to exclude irrelevant posts and redefine the search terms for the collection. Every single post can be rated on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 means that the post is irrelevant and 5 relevant (Figure 7). With every rating, content is re-ranked (see Section 3.3) and adapted to the user’s needs. Individual posts, users or even keywords can be excluded (Figure 29) to eliminate any irrelevant and unwanted content. If a post is totally irrelevant, the end user may select to exclude it from the collection. Moreover, irrelevant profiles and all of their published content can be excluded as well. Excluded posts are no longer displayed in the feed.

Figure 29: User/Item Exclusion

The exclusion of individual users can also be performed from the “Active Users” widget in the Dashboard view (Figure 30).

Figure 30: Exclude User

Beside user and/or post exclusion, keyword exclusion is also possible through the “Entities” widget in the Dashboard view (Figure 31). Any post(s) containing the excluded keyword(s) is then removed.

ENTITY	TYPE	FREQUENCY
medioambiente X Exclude	TAG	656
eco X Exclude	TAG	226
environment X Exclude	TAG	79
art X Exclude	TAG	68

Figure 31: Exclude Keyword

Any exclusion made by the end user is affecting the already gathered items but also prevents irrelevant items to be inserted in the collection at a future time.

For a better overview of the collection a new filter has been implemented, called “Unique”, with values False (default) and True. When set to True, all items containing almost the same text (near duplicate) are hidden and only the oldest is kept, avoiding the unnecessary repetition of the same information.

5.3 New and improved visualizations

In the Entities widget the end user can now inspect how the entities and their frequencies evolve over time, by clicking on the “Animate” button placed at the bottom right of the widget. Once the animation starts, the visualization panel is cleared, a stop/play button is placed below the graph and a date range is revealed at the bottom (Figure 32: Animation of Entities). The date range is created by setting the start date to the publication date of the oldest post inside the collection. The end date is set to the current date, if the collection is running, or to the date that it has stopped collecting posts. This time range is then divided to individual days from the beginning to the end. For each day, the entities and their frequencies are visualized. The end user can monitor the progress of the animation from the date range, as the active day is presented with red color. Along with the bubbles, the array with the absolute values (below the graph) is also updated from step to step. The end user may select at any point to pause the animation, to have a closer look to the current entities, and then resume it on demand.

Figure 32: Animation of Entities

The Feed view is presented with a gallery structure, but there was a need for a more compact presentation to allow easier browsing of large lists of posts. To this end, a list view of the posts (Figure 33) is created letting the user select the preferred display between gallery and list.

In the list view posts are placed in tabular form, presenting the columns, User, Text, Media, Date, Source, Popularity and Relevance. All columns, except Media, can be selected to sort the posts in a descending or ascending order. All data can be exported to .csv or .xls files.

User	Text	Media	Date	Source	Popularity	Relevance
YValdeluz	The latest The Environment Daily! https://t.co/H48ihqBhry Thanks to @infoventas5 @juangomezac @jmedelm #medioambiente	-	30 Oct 2017 at 14:22		0 retweets	1 2 3 4 5
radakko	The latest El Gatto Grigio! https://t.co/V7TchUns9G Thanks to @AyudaFelina @CostaRicaAyD @cdefgaba #medioambiente	-	30 Oct 2017 at 14:12		0 retweets	1 2 3 4 5
gelizetina	Even dirty electricity is cleaner with #electriccars. #miljo #environment #medioambiente https://t.co/K420AMQwMZ	-	30 Oct 2017 at 13:06		0 retweets	1 2 3 4 5
sambitoco	The latest Noticias SAMBITO! https://t.co/Rsv9gEmhye Thanks to @lasnotasverdes @monicoguera @AllYouNeedisEC #medioambiente	-	30 Oct 2017 at 12:52		0 retweets	1 2 3 4 5

Figure 33: List View

6 Integration and Pilot Support

In addition to the new analysis methodologies that were presented in the previous sections, considerable effort was dedicated to support the integration of the SMMT to the e-participation platform (Section 6.1), refine the REST API to reflect the new capabilities (Section 6.2), initialize the STEP pilot social media collections (Section 6.3), and to provide pilot partners with training in order to enable them to make good use of the SMMT (Section 6.5).

6.1 Integration with e-participation module

6.1.1 Automated translation

A variety of languages appear in the stream of collected social media posts, especially when the input configuration contains keywords in different languages, e.g. Bicicleta (Spanish for Bicycles). To make the results of the tool available to wider audiences of users, pilot users suggested that the user interface should support the automated translation of content items. To this end, we implemented the integration of the Machine Translation component offered by Linguatrec to the SMMT.

The available translation possibilities are presented in Table 22 and according to them and the selected language of the SMMT user interface, an appropriate translation direction is presented to end users. More specifically, if the SMMT user interface language is set to English, any post written in one of the pilot languages (Catalan, Italian, Greek, Spanish, and Turkish) can be translated to English. In the opposite case, if SMMT is set to one of the pilot languages, any post written in English can be translated to the respective language of the SMMT user interface.

Table 22: Translation direction values

Language Pair Value	Description
en-ca	English-Catalan
en-it	English-Italian
en-el	English-Greek
en-es	English-Spanish
en-tr	English-Turkish
ca-en	Catalan-English
it-en	Italian-English
el-en	Greek-English
es-en	Spanish-English
tr-en	Turkish-English

For all the posts, for which a translation is feasible given the previously described criteria, a “See Translation” button is placed to reveal the translation and a “Show in original” button to revert to the original post (Figure 34).

As soon as the end user clicks the “See translation” button the SMMT communicates with Linguatrec’s Machine Translation component through its API. Two parameters must be defined. The first one is the language pair (e.g. ‘en-es’) as defined in Table 22 and the second one is the text to be translated. The response of the API contains the translated text, fetched by SMMT and presented to the end user.

Figure 34: Translation of posts

A sample call to the Linguathec API is the following:

http://translate.linguec.org/TranslationService/Translate.aspx/translate?language_pair=es-en&text=La%20tasa%20de%20basura%20en%20los%20hogares%20pasar%C3%A1%20de%2053%20a%2033%20euros%20en%202018.%20https%3A%2F%2Ft.co%2FPhHKHA8Qng%20https%3A%2F%2Ft.co%2FMaxPOEjpk

In this example, we set the *language_pair* to *es-en* to indicate that we are interested in the Spanish to English translation of the text “La tasa de basura en los hogares pasará de 53 a 33 euros en 2018. <https://t.co/PhHKHA8Qng> <https://t.co/MaxPOEjpk>”, which leads to the following response:

```
{
  translation: "The rate of garbage in households from 53 to 33 euros in 2018. https://t.co/PhHKHA8Qng https://t.co/MaxPOEjpk"
}
```

6.1.2 Use of SMMT topics in e-participation module

For the citizens’ view, an enhanced scenario of usage is foreseen. In this respect, the conversations that a user is participating through the e-participation module will be enriched with relevant content items from social media that will be automatically discovered by the SMMT. To achieve that, the current discussions in the e-participation will feed the tool, which will then automatically extract relevant topics of interest. Subsequently social media monitoring will be performed based on those topics and the results will be returned to the citizens as suggested content items to be used in the conversations he/she participated in the STEP platform.

6.2 Updated REST API

Although there have been plenty of backend adaptations and extensions in the implementation of the REST API methods to support the new functionalities, the signature of most REST API methods remained almost the same as in the version presented in D4.3³⁴. The main change has been the addition of a new method to get the most relevant articles for a specific input collection (*GET /articles/collection={cid}*). Also, we have added additional parameters in the *GET /items* method to support the new filters, such as the unique filter or concept filters. Finally, the updated version includes methods to support relevance judgments and exclusion of specific items/users/keywords (as presented in Figure 29-Figure 31). These methods are presented in Table 23. A more detailed description of the API is available online³⁵.

³⁴ http://step4youth.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/D4.3_Social-media-monitoring-tool.pdf

³⁵ <http://smmt.step.green/doc/v0.1/>

Table 23: New methods included in the REST API of social media monitoring tool

Method	Description
GET /relevance/:cid/:iid	Get the relevance judgments for the item indicated by :iid with respect to the collection with id equals to :cid
GET /relevance/:cid	Get all the relevance judgments in the collection :cid
POST /relevance	Creates a new relevance judgment for a specific item in a specific collection. These parameters are passed in the body of the request as a json object with the following structure: <pre>{ "uid": uid, "cid": cid, "iid": iid, "relevance": relevance }</pre>
POST /collection/:cid/excludeItems	Exclude from the collection, defined by :cid, the items specified in the request body as a json array of item ids.
POST /collection/:cid/includeItems	Re-include in the collection the items specified in the request body as a json array of item ids.
POST /collection/:cid/excludeUsers	Exclude from the collection, defined by :cid, the users specified in the request body as a json array of user ids.
POST /collection/:cid/includeUsers	Re-include in the collection the users specified in the request body as a json array of user ids.
POST /collection/:cid/includeKeywords	Exclude from the collection, defined by :cid, the keywords specified in the request body as a json array.
POST /collection/:cid/excludeKeywords	Include in the collection, defined by :cid, the keywords specified in the body of the request as a json array.
GET /items	Returns a set of items, based on the query parameters specified in the call. Most parameters were implemented during the previous period: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collection={cid} parameter restricts the results only to items related to the specific collection. Otherwise the whole index is used. • since, until, source, language, type, original. Parameters to restrict results, based on time, • q="query", free text query. In the context of a collection has as a result, items that are relevant both to the collection and the query. • topicQuery="topic label". Used to get results related to a specific topic detected with the procedure presented in the first paragraph of section 3.2. New parameters include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • unique=true/false retrieve only unique content based on minhash • concept=climate_change Retrieve only items having the specific concept
GET /articles?collection=:cid	Returns articles related to the collection :cid, sorted by their popularity (number of shares in the whole collection). For pagination page, and numPerPage (default=1) query parameters can be used.

6.3 Performance optimizations

Due to the large amount of collected data, and the way this information is retrieved upon the selection of a collection, a number of optimization techniques were incorporated into the Social Media Monitoring Tool. First of all, we used memcached³⁶, as a layer in front of the REST API, in order to cache the responses of the API for a short time interval. More precisely, each response is cached for 15 minutes, meaning that over the next minutes the response will be served from memcached instead of recalculating it based on Solr and MongoDB. This improves significantly the response time, especially in the methods that calculate the statistics used by the dashboard of SMMT.

Despite the use of caching, the invalidation of the cache after expiration time, makes the tool slow in the first time the user visits a collection. To this end, we followed an auto-caching policy, by running a separate service that periodically visits each of the collections in the system, and recaches all the methods needed for the proper visualization of the collection in the UI. In that way, a user always gets a cached but recent version of the collections.

To improve also the way data is indexed and queried in Solr, we took advantage of the DocValues³⁷ which are a way of storing field values internally in Solr, optimized for faceting. For that purpose, the fields that are used for facet queries in our API (e.g. user followers to support REACH or items likes to calculate endorsements) are configured as DocValues, while for fields that are used both for filtering and faceting, we index them twice using a different configuration for each of these functionalities. This setting improves the response time of Solr, although this optimization is not perceived by the end user due to the caching policy mentioned before. However the better memory management that accompanies this feature, has as a result the avoidance of “out of memory” errors which had been often occurring in very large collections in the previous version of the SMMT.

6.4 Pilot configuration

To initiate the collection of social media content for all the dialogues in the platform, we created a separate collection for each dialogue using a set of keywords and accounts provided by the pilots. These are summarized in Table 24. Note that in most cases the input is broader with respect to the geographical region of each pilot. In other words, only a small portion of the collected content originates from the exact region of each pilot.

Table 24: Input configuration for each of the dialogue in STEP platform. The keywords and accounts of each of the dialogues were provided by the corresponding pilot.

Dialogue	Input	
	Keywords / hashtags	Accounts
<i>EU Pilot</i>		
Tacking Climate Change	Climatechange, Climateaction, step4climatechange, climatechangeisreal	Twitter accounts: @ClimateCEE, @climate_reality, @ClimateAdapt, @climateadaptH2O, @AdaptClimate Facebook pages: STEP4youth
17 Global Sustainable Development Goals	Sdgs, Globalgoals, agenda2030, sustainabledevelopment, Gsdgoals, Makepovertyhistory, Genderequality, humanrights,	Twitter accounts: @UN, @ESG_SDG, @SDGaction, @UNSDSN, @UNCCD, @Youth4SDG, @Action4SD Facebook pages: SDGaction,

³⁶ <http://memcached.org/>

³⁷ https://lucene.apache.org/solr/guide/6_6/docvalues.html

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

	act4sdgs	SDGYouthAdvocacyCaribbean, Sdgsociety, Unvolunteers, globalgoalsUN, YouthForGlobalGoals <i>YouTube channels: The Global Goals</i>
<i>Region of Crete Pilot</i>		
Προστασία και διαχείριση υδάτων στην Κρήτη. / Waste Water	Watermanagement, Waterreuse, Savewater, Undergroundwater, ανακύκλωση νερού, εξοικονόμηση νερού, water management, water reuse, save water, underground water	<i>Twitter accounts: @efitsolaki, @WateRRTreatment, @OWNWMI, @eureau, @wasteintowater, @WaterWasteProc, @Waterjournaluk</i> <i>Facebook pages: Water&Waste</i> <i>Google+ account: Don't Wait and Waste Water</i>
Προστατευόμενα είδη δικτύου Natura στην Κρήτη - Η περίπτωση της θαλάσσιας χελώνας Caretta-Caretta / The protection of Caretta-Caretta in Crete.	Carettacaretta Seaturtlesgreece Seaturtlecrete caretta caretta sea turtle crete sea turtle greece	<i>Twitter accounts: @OBXNEST, @SeaTurtleNews, @Seaturtle, @Tortoiseblog, @Turtlenews, @SEEturtles, @Archelon_stps, @Turtletweets, @WildlifeSense, @MEDASSET, @Gtrismpioti</i> <i>Facebook pages: Caretta Caretta National Turtle Park, ArchelonLakonikos2015, Archelonzakynthos, Kyparissiabayproject, Archelonrethymno, Archelonkoroni, Conserveturtles, archelon.gr, ARCHELON Crete, Archelonrc, LifeEuroturtles, AmvrakikosTurtles, carettaкотychi, seaturtles</i> <i>YouTube channels: MEDASSET, Caretta Archelon</i>
Περιοχές δικτύου Natura 2000 Κρήτης / Areas of the Natura 2000 network in Crete	natura2000, natura2000day, biodiversity, eunature, βιοποικιλότητα οικοσύστημα, ecosystem environment	<i>Twitter accounts: @Joaoamarosilva, @AntoniosMazaris, @natura2000tr, @Natura2000value, @Natura2000DAY, @HermanSnijders, @Natura2000brand, @Biodiversitygr</i> <i>Facebook pages: natura2000turkey, EU - Natura 2000</i> <i>YouTube channels: NHMC Ecology Lab</i> <i>Google+ accounts: Biodiversity Professionals, Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services Network (BESNet), Biodiversity GR, The Biodiversity Group</i>
Προσαρμογή στην Κλιματική αλλαγή / Adaptation to climate change	Climatechange, climate change, κλιματική αλλαγή	-
<i>Mollet de Valles Pilot</i>		
Antirumors (Grup de treball)	Racisme, Convivència Comerç, renda garantida, ús sanitat	-
Resultats de la trobada participativa pel Pla Local de Prevenció de Residus / Results of the participatory meeting for the Local Plan for Waste Prevention	Residus, Reciclatge, medi ambient, compostatge, ciutats netes, contaminació, prevenció de residus	-
Consulta les propostes del Viver de projectes juvenils de Mollet del Valles 2017	accions juvenils, espacios para jóvenes, electrodance batallas rap, lucha robots	-
Sostenibilitat a Mollet (INS Gallecs) / Sustainability in Mollet	Residus, Reciclatge, medi ambient, compostatge, ciutats netes, contaminació, sostenibilitat	-

Espai Consell de la Ciutat Mollet / Space Council of the Mollet City	Participació, consell de ciutat, empoderament, xarxes associatives, ciutadanes	-
<i>Valdemoro Pilot</i>		
El medio ambiente en imagenes / The environment in images	Valdemoroverde, #valdemorosaludable, #valdemoroenimagenes	<i>Twitter accounts:</i> @Ayto_Valdemoro, @sera_alcalde <i>Facebook pages:</i> STEPValdemoro, Valdemoroayuntamiento, seraalcalde
Transporte ecológico / Ecological transport	Bicisenvaldemoro, Movilidadenvaldemoro, Valdemorotransporte, Bicisenvaldemoro, movilidadenvaldemoro	<i>Twitter accounts:</i> @Ayto_Valdemoro, @sera_alcalde <i>Facebook pages:</i> STEPValdemoro, Valdemoroayuntamiento, seraalcalde
<i>Locride Pilot</i>		
Discariche e gestione rifiuti nella Locride / Landfills and waste management in Locride	Rifiuti, Discariche gestione rifiuti, locride	-
<i>Hatay Pilot</i>		
Hep Birlikte El Ele Temiz bir Hatay Bizimle / Together we have a clean Hatay	Temizbirhatay, Yesilbirhatay, Stephatay, step hatay, temiz bir hatay, yesilbir hatay, hatay bizimle	<i>Twitter accounts:</i> @HatayBSB, @EXPOHatay2021 <i>Facebook pages:</i> HatayBld, LutfuSavas

6.5 User training sessions

To help educate pilot users on the optimal use of the tool, CERTH organized a series of training sessions (5-9/11/2016). In particular, two webinars per pilot were organized with the objectives of presenting a set of educational videos on the use of the STEP SMMT and responding live to questions of the audience. The videos were produced by the CERTH team and consisted of an online video manual that explains how users can:

- Start monitoring a topic of interest in STEP (<https://goo.gl/fdGm14>)
- Browse through their collections and customize them (<https://goo.gl/txnTBE>)
- Browse through the content of a collection (<https://goo.gl/34kxiY>)
- Refine the content of a collection to find valuable information (<https://goo.gl/V2svng>)
- Perform free text search in collections (<https://goo.gl/kSY4vF>)
- Gain insights from collected data (<https://goo.gl/ytyPxX>)

The educational videos were made publicly available on the STEP YouTube channel to encourage self-paced online training and allow users to review them at their convenience any time. The second webinar involved an additional Q&A session with pilot partners that helped them better understand the usage of the tool and leverage it for monitoring and supporting their campaigns in STEP.

STEP Social Media Monitoring Tool

6 βίντεο • 143 προβολές • Τελευταία ενημέρωση στις 20 Οκτ 2016

Step Horizon2020 **ΕΓΓΡΑΦΗ 5**

- 1 **How do I start monitoring a topic of interest in STEP?**
Step Horizon2020 4:31
- 2 **How do I browse through my collections and customize them?**
Step Horizon2020 5:54
- 3 **How do I browse through the content of a collection?**
Step Horizon2020 2:54
- 4 **How do I refine the content of a collection to find valuable information?**
Step Horizon2020 2:11
- 5 **How do I perform free text search in collections?**
Step Horizon2020 5:30
- 6 **How do I gain insights from collected data?**
Step Horizon2020 6:09

Figure 35: Educational videos of the STEP SMMT on YouTube

7 Evaluation

Several of the previous sections presented a data-driven evaluation of some key components of the SMMT, e.g. Section 3 of the content classification and topic detection components, and Section 4 of the audience mining component of the tool. This section provides the results of an *end-to-end* evaluation, first by presenting an analysis of the collected STEP pilot data (Section 7.1) and then by discussing the outcomes of a user-centred evaluation workshop that was conducted as part of the final project consortium meeting in Hatay (Section 0). The reported results provide a glimpse into the capabilities of the delivered tool for monitoring and making sense of social media discussions as well as into the perceptions of end users into its usefulness and value in practical contexts.

7.1 Pilot data analysis

Reaching out to the public and boosting engagement in decision making seems increasingly important for local governments in the age of Internet and social media. Mining social media, provides new insights on the perceptions of citizens with regards to public authorities, local emerging topics of interest and public acceptance. For public relations, provision of new communication channels and citizen engagement in the decision making, social media data analytics are a useful tool in the hands of local governments. Furthermore, understanding social media data is critical for the success of a campaign especially given the fact that budget and resources are currently limited.

To analyze social media discussions of relevance to STEP, we applied the topic detection techniques of section 3.2 in the dialogues created by the pilots of STEP. Since the content of each dialogue is in a different language, depending on the pilot, we used the main language of each collection to apply topic detection only for the subset of posts in the particular language. More specifically, we used Spanish for the dialogues of Valdemoro, Catalan or Spanish for Mollet de Valles, Turkish for the posts from Hatay and Italian for Locride. For the posts coming from the dialogues of the Region of Crete we used only English, as most relevant posts were in English. For the dialogues of the EU pilot, we also used English. Due to the size constraint, i.e. dialogues with more than 500 posts, we limited the topic detection and analysis only to a subset of the STEP dialogues. Table 25 presents a summary of these dialogues, by depicting the number of posts for each of them, the number of associated articles extracted, and finally the number of detected topics in posts or articles, either by using LDA or NMF. In most of the dialogues the number of topics for the posts is 40, which is the upper limit of topics. Regarding the articles, extracted from the URLs shared in the posts, their portion compared to the size of the posts collection varies significantly. This observation indicates that, from dialogue to dialogue, different types of URLs are shared, with some dialogues, where posts link more frequently to articles than others. The detected topics in articles are also 40 in most cases due to the large number of articles.

Next, we tried to analyze these results, and investigate whether detected topics can help in the exploration of dialogues and their deeper understanding. For each of the dialogues in the pilots of EU and Region of Crete³⁸, we inspected the most important LDA topic in the posts in terms of their prevalence $P(T)$, trying to understand their main aspect and how these are related to the dialogue. For a most detailed view in the topics, the reader is referred to the online instance of the SMMT^{39 40}.

³⁸ Evaluation of topics detected in the dialogues of Locride, Hatay, Valdemoro and Mollet de Valles was not done because of the language used in these dialogues.

³⁹ <http://smtt.step.green>

⁴⁰ A link to the topics detected for each of the dialogues, can be found in the end of the simplified design, presented in section 5.1. For example, in the eu dialogue about sustainable goals the simplified page can be found here: <http://smtt.step.green/ui/specified/municipality.html?dialogue=16605eu1507197778243>

The first of the two dialogues of the EU pilot are related to climate change. The main LDA topic detected in the posts is depicted in Table 26. The most important among the detected topics is that referring to the means that can be used to mitigate, prevent and stop climate change. In general, the 168 posts associated with this topic are related to latest news about climate change, and also posts about consumer's awareness in the matter. There are also several documents that appeared to be irrelevant but as they have a low probability of belonging to the topic, they can be easily detected and discarded. It is worth noting that the existence of noisy documents is a characteristic of the large topics, in terms of associated documents. Topics with fewer posts are usually of better quality. For example, in the same dialogue, the second most prevalent topic (topic 7 in Figure 5), consists of 26 posts, and is related with the cost of climate change in the economy. In this topic, all of the documents have a comparably high probability of belonging to it.

Table 25: Summary of the dialogues used for topic detection. The posts corresponding only to original content after discarding shares and retweets. Articles have been extracted from the URLs in these posts.

Dialogue	Posts			Articles		
	#posts	LDA topics	NMF topics	#articles	LDA topics	NMF topics
<i>EU Pilot</i>						
Tacking Climate Change	5,841	40	40	1,922	40	40
17 Global Sustainable Development Goals	24,927	40	40	5,271	40	40
<i>Region of Crete Pilot</i>						
Προστασία και διαχείριση υδάτων στην Κρήτη / Waste Water	20,029	40	40	3,022	40	40
Προστατευόμενα είδη δικτύου Natura στην Κρήτη-χελώνας Caretta-Caretta / The protection of Caretta-Caretta in Crete.	1,478	38	38	601	24	24
Περιοχές δικτύου Natura 2000 Κρήτης / Areas of the Natura 2000 network in Crete	9,832	40	40	1,858	40	40
Προσαρμογή στην Κλιματική αλλαγή / Adaptation to climate change	5,657	40	40	1,875	40	40
<i>Mollet de Valles Pilot</i>						
Antirumors (Grup de treball)	2,125	40	40	-	-	-
Resultats de la trobada participativa pel Pla Local de Prevenció de Residus / Results of the participatory meeting for the Local Plan for Waste Prevention	4,260	40	40	116	10	10
Consulta les propostes del Viver de projectes juvenils de Mollet del Valles 2017	1,911	40	40	-	-	-
Sostenibilitat a Mollet (INS Gallecs) / Sustainability in Mollet	4,933	40	40	124	11	11
Espai Consell de la Ciutat Mollet / Space Council of the Mollet City	3,480	40	40	-	-	-
<i>Valdemoro Pilot</i>						
El medio ambiente en imagenes / The environment in images	30,129	40	40	3,794	40	40
Transporte ecológico / Ecological transport	1,768	40	40	61	7	7
<i>Locride Pilot</i>						
Discariche e gestione rifiuti nella Locride / Landfills and waste management in Locride	15,418	40	40	3,423	40	40
<i>Hatay Pilot</i>						
Hep Birlikte El Ele Temiz bir Hatay Bizimle / Together we have a clean Hatay	1,172	34	34	-	-	-

The main topic of the second dialogue, also depicted in Table 26 is related to the Unitus Seed Fund⁴¹ and how its investments are associated with the sustainable developments goals of United Nations. This consists of 1,572 posts of very high probability (>0.9); yet, the content of most of them is quite similar as most of them are tweets originating from the same initial article.

Table 26: Most prevalent topic detected in the posts of the two dialogues of EU pilot.

EU Pilot			
Dialogue: Tracking Climate Change			
Topic	4	Prevalence	0.118
Terms	climate change latest daily prevent necessary mitigation consumers awareness		
Description	Latest news about climate change as posted by news sites		
#Documents	168		
Dialogue: 17 Global Sustainable Development Goals			
Topic	8	Prevalence	0.082
Terms	Fund seed unitus mapping		
Description	Investments of Unitus Seed Fund to GSDG of United Nations		
#Documents	1572		

Tackling climate change is an essential topic of interest both at EU and local level. As the dialogue per se is very broad, it would be really beneficial for EU officials to understand exactly what do Europeans say and share with regards to climate change on social media, which is the most popular channel where climate related discussion takes place, who are the influential users that would influence public opinion. SMMT would ideally serve as a toolbox to uncover such insights by mining and surfacing social media data. EU officials would then leverage the knowledge gained, to design and bring about new climate change related initiatives, achieve improve budget and resource allocation, involve more people in discussions and decision making and boost participation in more platforms.

Digging deeper into *Tackling Climate Change* dialogue with SMMT, EU officials would certify that it is a topic that really concerns Europeans. As of today, there are approximately 160,000 posts made, by more than 65,000 users. Reach is estimated to 160,000 users and 24,000 endorsements. The activity timeline would help officers understand periodicities or what fosters discussions. In such way, bursts could be anticipated too and public relations would improve their response strategies for potential crisis management.

The “Articles” widget would help officers understand that the main topics of concern pertain to *Sea Levels Rising* and the *Need to act on climate change (to ensure our future)*. As a consequence, new EU-wide initiatives should consider shifting the focus and allocate more resources to these two topics. Influencers that are reported in the tool could also be utilized as engagement drivers. Last but not least, by exploiting the topics and articles’ analysis, officials would have the opportunity to explore what is being said and shared with regards to Oceans level rising and tap into relevant discussions.

In case of the dialogues of the region of Crete, we opted to analyze two of them related to the protection of Caretta Caretta turtle and the network of Natura 2000⁴² respectively. Regarding Natura 2000 dialogue, the main topic consists of 167 posts and is related to how the climate change affects agro-biodiversity and subsequently food security. Given that the collection of social media posts for that specific dialogue was initiated with the keyword “biodiversity” among others, we can conclude that the topic is relevant. Investigating the next topics, we observed that most of them are also related to different aspects of biodiversity, which seems to overwhelm the content of the dialogue. For example the second topic (topic 6)

⁴¹ <https://usf.vc/>

⁴² <http://www.natura.org/>

is mostly related to biodiversity in areas of Spain. For caretta-caretta dialogue, the most prevalent topic consists of YouTube videos with Caretta Caretta turtles swimming near the Turkish coast and near the Greek island of Zakynthos. The main reason for which these posts were included in the same topic is the repetition of words like, Caretta Caretta, swim, loggerhead (another name for Caretta Caretta), Zakynthos and Turkey.

Table 27: Most prevalent topic detected in two of the dialogues of EU pilot.

Region of Crete			
Dialogue: Προστατευόμενα είδη δικτύου Natura στην Κρήτη-Η περίπτωση της θαλάσσιας χελώνας Caretta-Caretta / The protection of Caretta-Caretta in Crete.			
Topic	37	Prevalence	0.155
Terms	Caretta zakynthos turkey whales music loggerhead		
Description	Caretta-caretta appearances in the coast of Turkey and Zakynthos		
Documents	99		
Dialogue: Περιοχές δικτύου Natura 2000 Κρήτης / Areas of the Natura 2000 network in Crete			
Topic	9	Prevalence	0.073
Terms	Climate food change national ecosystem unsustainable security		
Description	Affection of climate change in agro-bidiversity and food security		
Documents	167		

7.2 User evaluation workshops

With the workshop set up of the evaluation plan, we aimed at proposing a pilot-centred methodology for the assessment of the various features and functionalities of the STEP SMMT. More specifically, we were interested in assessing a) whether the STEP SMMT individual components are working as expected and specified, b) the different widgets that are integrated in the system work well together to deliver valuable insights to the user, c) the overall system and the interface is understandable and usable by the target group (public administrations).

During the meeting in Hatay (9-10/10/2017), we organized an evaluation workshop where pilot partners (public administrators) tested the system and completed a number of predefined tasks to evaluate and give feedback to technical partners regarding the quality of the results and usability of the system.

Partners from the five STEP pilot sites were guided through a discussion on the evaluation issues under examination and the evaluation purpose. To provide a basis for analysis, questionnaires were given to the participants. Through the use of rating scales and open-ended questions, responses were collected and evaluated providing valuable information on PA officers' preferences. We designed the questionnaires to reflect the newly added features and functionalities of the system namely social mix, timeline, heatmap, active users, entities, filtering, search as well as to provide users with insights on the overall system. For the construction of our questionnaire we relied on the approach described in the study of (Laugwitz, Held and Schrepp, 2008). This reports how to construct end user questionnaires to measure user experience quickly in a simple and immediate way while covering a preferably comprehensive impression of the product user experience. The framework assumes that perceived ergonomic quality and perceived hedonic quality describe independent dimensions of the user experience and therefore the questionnaire contains items which measure the perceived attractiveness directly as well as items, which measure the quality of the product on the relevant aspects in a given usage scenario.

Consequently, we aimed at evaluating the tool in terms of:

- 🔴 **Utility:** Does the user perceive the functions in the system as useful and fit for the purpose?
- 🔴 **Usability:** Does the user feel that it is easy and efficient to get things done with the system?
- 🔴 **Stimulation:** Does the system give inspiration or enhanced experience to the user?
- 🔴 **Value:** Is the system important to the user? What is its value?

Last but not least, as we considered the exploitation of the project as very important we also wanted to make a preliminary evaluation of the market potential of the proposed solution. Consequently, we were interested in assessing whether the system is performing better compared to the baseline (manual search via Twitter or other social media) and other free social media monitoring solutions like TAGBOARD⁴³. TAGBOARD uses hashtags to search for and collect public social media within seconds of being posted to networks like Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook and a demo is provided currently online for free. Clearly, TAGBOARD represents a competitive offering available in the market and since it also provides users the opportunity to discover it for free it was considered to be one strong market competitor that is relevant for our study and representative of numerous commercial social media monitoring solutions.

As will be demonstrated in the following sections, the results of this discussion were very encouraging regarding the performance of the tool.

⁴³ <https://tagboard.com/>

Figure 36: The UI of TAGBOARD. Sample Results for #natura2000

Evaluators (pilot users) that participated in the Hatay Workshop were asked to perform a set of tasks that involved interaction with online tools. Immediately after completing each task they were asked to fill a questionnaire that had been distributed to them a few days prior to the workshop. This comprised both qualitative and quantitative responses; these are intended to capture the users' experience concerning the principal and unique features of STEP SMMT derived from the tasks. Each end user was requested to look for further details and information on environmental issues of their interest concerning their region:

- ❶ Mollet was asked to search and identify insights on “Antirumors (Grup de treball)” (Workgroup on Anti-rumors)
- ❷ Valdemoro was asked to search and identify insights on “Valdemoro verde – Medioambiente “ (Green Valdemoro – Environment)
- ❸ Crete was asked to search and identify insights on “Περιοχές δικτύου Natura 2000 Κρήτης” (NATURA 2000 sites in Crete)
- ❹ Hatay was asked to search and identify insights on “Hep Birlikte El Ele Temiz bir Hatay Bizimle” (Together we have a clean Hatay)
- ❺ Locride was asked to search and identify insights on “Discariche e gestione rifiuti nella Locride” (Landfills and waste management in Locride)

At first, they were asked to utilize Facebook, Twitter, Instagram or any other social media of their preference to list three topics/stories related to the main topic, 3 influencers, 3 multimedia posts and 3 of the most recent posts that were the most interesting. Their consecutive task was to identify the same active users and types of posts by utilizing a social media monitoring tool (TAGBOARD) that is provided for free. Last but not least they were probed to list the same content by utilizing the SMMT provided by STEP. It is important to underline that although basic search through all social media did provide some results, out of 5 municipalities only one (Mollet) was able to retrieve and list some answers for the information requested using the online tool TAGBOARD. Valdemoro was also able to retrieve useful data but only 1 per request and the evaluator was unable to assess the user interface, usefulness and usability of the tool. Overall, users were neither satisfied with TAGBOARD's user interface nor with the features and insights that it provided. Indicative answers report that:

“I cannot find a suitable #hashtag so that I can get results for the Natura 2000 areas in Crete”, “From the results in English, I can't understand the influence each post has”,

Municipality of Crete .

“TAGBOARD search engine is really strict and shows not so much result, Municipality of Hatay

Also in terms of user acceptance, usability and user attractiveness, the STEP SMMT outperformed TAGBOARD across all attributes that were evaluated. According to questionnaires distributed to pilot users, to evaluate a user interface like the one that STEP proposes it is important to test the following attributes of a system (Laugwitz, Held and Schrepp, 2008):

- Easy
- Interesting
- Satisfying
- Valuable
- Efficient
- Clear
- Innovative

In a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 corresponds to the worst and 5 the best score, the STEP SMMT achieved very good rating from users in all these fields.

Figure 37: How do users perceive TAGBOARD's user interface as compared to the STEP Social Media Monitoring Tool's interface

Table 28 outlines the average scores and standard deviation of responses for all tested attributes.

Table 28: TAGBOARD's UI evaluation. Average scores and standard deviation

	SMMT		TAGBOARD	
	Average (across all pilots)	Standard Deviation	Average (across all pilots)	Standard Deviation
easy	4.4	1.34	3	0.82
interesting	4.4	0.89	2.5	1.00
satisfying	3.8	1.10	1.25	0.50
valuable	4.4	0.89	1.5	0.58
efficient	4	1.22	1.25	0.50
clear	4.4	0.89	2.25	0.50
innovative	4.2	1.30	2.25	0.96

The collected feedback statistics suggest that TAGBOARD is not considered very innovative or leading edge. On the other hand, regarding SMMT it appears that the insights that the tool provides and the user friendly design ultimately met user expectations and attracted their interest. This observation further supports the added value of the platform and the exploitation potential of the project.

Locride, however, was critical of the performance of both TAGBOARD and STEP SMMT. The evaluator was unable to list 3 stories/topics related to the main topic, 3 influencers, 3 multimedia posts and 3 of the most recent posts that are the most interesting to them utilizing either of the tools. As they comment:

«Tagboard is not useful tool and complicated to learn. The social media monitoring tool has a nice interface and a lot of potential but it should be improved in collecting information. Some filters don't work properly. Once these issues will be fixed then the social media monitoring tool can be a useful tool for a public officer to collect and monitor trends and ideas».

Municipality of Locride

To assess this qualitative result, CERTH repeated the evaluation tasks of the Locride Municipality and no problem was identified with the use of filters or the availability of information in the collections. This finding indicates that probably more effort should be placed on user training so that inexperienced users can make the most out of the system. Moreover, according to the evaluator, the low quality of collected content could be largely attributed to the poor level of debate and discussions about environmental issues on social networks in the Locride area.

An important part of the evaluation focused on the usability and user acceptance of the tool that we have developed in the context of STEP. The results (Figure 38-Figure 40) were encouraging.

Figure 38 : Relevance assessments of SMMT results

Figure 39 : STEP SMMT - Evaluation of the widgets

Figure 40: How understandable are the various widgets of the tool

Four out of five municipalities are quite satisfied with the quality and relevance of the results. It seems from the graph that the “Heatmap” widget is considered to be the least relevant. However this can be attributed to users not being familiarized with the idea and the representation of a heatmap. Again, Locride gave a poor evaluation of the results relevance (Figure 41).

Figure 41: Rating of the usefulness of the filters

Most participants support that the filters work well although the importance of practice and training is underlined so that they can really leverage the functionalities of the tool. After using the tool to actually search for specific insights, stories and influencers evaluators also came to a general conclusion regarding the use of hashtags in social media. More specifically, the evaluator from Valdemoro supports that the use of hashtags is difficult and hard when it comes to specific and very localized topics.

Participants were also requested to provide an overall free text assessment of the value of all the different tools they utilized to accomplish the task. STEP SMMT clearly outperformed both the baseline (searching manually through various social media) and TAGBOARD, although there is room for improvement. In detail users feel that:

“To search separately in each social media takes a long time and is not useful”, “SMMT is easy to use and shows a lot of results which you can exclude if it is not relevant”

Hatay Municipality

“Free search in social media is what a municipality does if it does not have STEP or other tools in specialists’ offices. Obviously it is not efficient and we do have the need to have a tool that eases our work” “SMMT seems to be the most complete tool offering a large range of possibilities. The downside could be the expertise to use it getting the most of it but this could be solved offering support to the municipality with the first searches”

Mollet Municipality

“SMMT is very simple and intuitive and it may be of great support for some kind of initiatives.”

Valdemoro Municipality

“The Social Tracker tool was much more efficient and quick as it could combine all social media and as many keywords as needed. The results can be easily filtered to help you target in most interesting posts instead of searching again from the beginning. It is also very important to find most active users in order to establish better communication with them. It is also very important that the search outcome is not influenced by my followers which happens when searching to Facebook”

Municipality of Crete.

To sum it up, the results indicated that the STEP SMMT was judged positively in terms of being easy to use, innovative and useful by municipality users. Discrepancies in responses may reflect the impact of having to complete a cognitively demanding task with a novel tool and therefore the importance of training. The responses that participants gave in both the tasks and the open ended items shed light on their attitude to a number of key functions including insights provided by the tool, the usefulness of the widgets, the availability of accompanying multimedia, the influencers and the utility of the tool. The STEP SMMT seems to clearly outperform both the baseline (manual search through social media) and existing online free solutions (TAGBOARD) although further benchmarking with other commercially available tools would be suggested as a stage before bringing the tool to the market.

7.3 Teenagers’ questionnaire analysis

To assess the SMMT platform from citizen perspective – with emphasis on younger groups – the consortium organized an event that took place in a high school in Catalonia. The audience comprised 26 participants, 15-16 years old of whom 46.2% were male, 46.2% female and 7.7% gender neutral.

Users were asked to perform a small number of tasks to get familiar with the system, the functionalities and the results that it provides. More specifically they were asked to name 3 environmental topics of their interest (among the ones that the system provides), the 5 top user locations and then they were requested to list the 3 most popular concepts as well as the 3 most active users according to the system. The vast majority of respondents expressed their interest in the topics of electric vehicles, waste management and solar energy.

As the following diagram shows 73.1% were able to find interesting topics related to the environment within SMMT.

Figure 42: Where you able to find interested topics related to the environment within SMMT? (Si: Yes, No: NO, N/S: NA)

A Likert type question was given to participants to measure their opinions regarding the usability and user friendliness of the system as well as the relevance of the results. Respondents were offered a choice of seven pre-determined responses with the neutral point being neither agree nor disagree. Diagrams in Figures 43 and 44 demonstrate to what extent users agree with a variety of statements concerning the evaluation of the platform.

Figure 43: To what extent do you agree with the following statements. From left to right:
 (1) Overall, I am satisfied with how easy it is to use SMMT
 (2) I was able to complete the tasks and scenarios quickly using SMMT
 (3) I believe I could become productive quickly using SMMT
 (4) Whenever I made a mistake using the system I could recover easily and quickly

The vast majority of participants (20/26) believe that it is easy to use SMMT (they selected *Totally Agree*, *Agree*, *Somewhat agree* and were able to complete the tasks quickly. However, when requested if they could recover easily and quickly whenever they made a mistake there were 9 participants that claimed to face difficulties (as they *Somewhat Disagree* or *Disagree* with the fourth question (Figure 43). This might suggest that we should enrich the system with better explanations on mouse over actions or provide a user guide.

Figure 44: To what extent do you agree with the following statements. From left to right:
 (5) The organization of information on the SMMT screens was clear
 (6) The interface was pleasant
 (7) I can count on the information I get on this system
 (8) The information on this system is valuable
 (9) The results are very relevant to my search
 (10) Filters work great
 (11) I will likely suggest SMMT to a friend

Judging from the diagrams in Figure 44 it appears that evaluators were satisfied with the relevance of the results and the functionality of the system. However, when calculating the weighted average of responses in the final item “I will likely suggest SMMT to a friend” the result is 3.67, close to a neutral opinion.

The following table (Table 29) summarizes the satisfaction of participants with regards to the information presented in the widgets. The satisfaction was estimated as a weighted average of the responses of participants provided in a Likert scale where 1 represents *Very Dissatisfied* and 7 *Very Satisfied*.

Table 29: Widgets' Weighted Average Table

Widget	Weighted Average
Feed	4.85
Social Mix	4.85
Timeline	5
Active Users	5.28
Entities	4.96

As it appears on the table, participants’ favorite widget is *Active Users* followed by the *Timeline* and the *Entities*.

Overall, responses expressed the satisfaction of end users. In particular when asked to rate SMMT as a platform in a scale of 1 to 10, SMMT scored an average of 7.34. Given the age of the respondents and the fact that this is the first time they interacted with such a tool, this score is assessed to indicate a satisfactory level of acceptance by end users. What some participants (6 out of 26) found frustrating is the feeling that finding information is difficult and/or confusing. Others (7 out of 26) support that it should provide better sorting options (sort by theme, views or order of visits). Oddly though, on the positive side when asked about what do they like best, approximately 9 out of 26 users stated that the tool is easy to use, presents lots of interesting information. Many users also particularly enjoyed the look and feel and interaction with the tool and believe that it is practical and useful.

8 Conclusions and Future Work

This deliverable provided a report of the updates and new developments that took place with respect to the Social Media Monitoring Tool during the second project period. Numerous improvements and new capabilities have been added to the SMMT, with a focus on improving the relevance of the collected content, analyzing the structure of discussed topics and studying the social media communities and users around the project and its pilots. At the same, the user interface of the tool was redesigned with the goal of making it more accessible and usable for end users. The conducted evaluations demonstrated that the tool was effective in surfacing relevant content for PA users who were in charge of the STEP pilots and in giving them an easy way to delve into discussions of interest for their region, as well as in identifying relevant actors for supporting the outreach and engagement activities of the project. The SMMT also improved in terms of reliability and responsiveness as a result of several optimizations that were implemented in the back-end. A technical demonstration of the tool was given in the context of the 2017 edition of the Internet Science conference and a summary of its architecture and components will be included in the conference proceedings.

Given that the tool has reached a state of high technical maturity and value, the development team plans to actively maintain and extend it with a dual goal: a) support future research in the area of social media mining and retrieval through a robust and extensible open-source solution, b) explore commercial uses of the tool, both as part of the joint exploitation strategy of the project, and as a standalone solution that can be catered for the particular requirements of different sectors (beyond municipal and regional public authorities).

To maximize the impact of the tool, i.e. its uptake by the research community and its commercial value, we foresee that a number of extensions will be beneficial. These include:

- Addition of a layer dealing with advanced user management, i.e. granting access rights and privileges to different categories of end users, e.g. read-only, configuring collections, administering users, etc.
- Support of additional languages, both at a front-end level (by translating UI controls) and at the back-end (by extending the topic classification and relevance models).
- Improving the newly added relevance filters and adding more topic classifiers to make the tool appealing and valuable for different domains (e.g. marketing, security, etc.).
- Integrating complex graph-based visualizations, as the ones presented in Section 4 in the real-time operation and view of the tool.
- Testing larger scale deployments on distributed infrastructure (the current STEP instance is installed and operated from a single server).

9 References

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10 Appendix I

Table 30-Table 39 present the evaluation results for post classification (first and second classification steps) for Greek, Spanish, Italian, Turkish and Catalan language. Table 40 lists the keywords for post retrieval for each concept. Table 41-Table 45 present the complete results of the relevant and influential account discovery methods from Section 4. Finally, Figure 45-Figure 50 depict the discovered communities of STEP_H2020 Twitter account follower network.

Table 30: First classifier details (Greek)

Classes	# examples	Precision	Recall
relevant	1500	84.9%	80.4%
irrelevant	1500	81.2%	85.3%

Table 31: Second classifier details (Greek)

Second classifier	# examples	Precision	Recall
ecology	180	49.2%	51.2%
eco-efficiency	180	61.2%	61.8%
climate change	220	70.1%	71.2%
waste	200	58.1%	57.2%
water protection	200	46.2%	45.7%
environmental policy	160	59.2%	57.4%
land degradation	180	53.9%	51.1%
urban environment	180	60.2%	58.2%

Table 32: First classifier details (Spanish)

Classes	# examples	Precision	Recall
relevant	1500	86.0%	82.1%
irrelevant	1500	83.5%	87.1%

Table 33: Second classifier details (Spanish)

Second classifier	# examples	Precision	Recall
ecology	180	52.1%	50.4%
eco-efficiency	180	62.2%	60.8%
climate change	220	70.2%	70.9%
waste	200	56.1%	55.6%
water protection	200	45.6%	44.4%
environmental policy	160	60.7%	57.8%
land degradation	180	53.7%	52.1%
urban environment	180	64.6%	59.7%

Table 34: First classifier details (Italian)

Classes	# examples	Precision	Recall
relevant	1500	86.8%	81.2%
irrelevant	1500	82.9%	88.1%

Table 35: Second classifier details (Italian)

Second classifier	# examples	Precision	Recall
ecology	180	47.7%	50.1%

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

eco-efficiency	180	60.2%	61.0%
climate change	220	67.2%	68.4%
waste	200	55.1%	55.3%
water protection	200	43.6%	42.2%
environmental policy	160	58.7%	56.7%
land degradation	180	50.0%	50.0%
urban environment	180	61.6%	58.7%

Table 36: First classifier details (Turkish)

Classes	# examples	Precision	Recall
relevant	1500	85.6%	79.1%
irrelevant	1500	81.7%	87.1%

Table 37: Second classifier details (Turkish)

Second classifier	# examples	Precision	Recall
ecology	180	49.1%	50.7%
eco-efficiency	180	61.3%	61.2%
climate change	220	68.7%	70.1%
waste	200	54.1%	54.6%
water protection	200	43.7%	43.1%
environmental policy	160	57.9%	55.8%
land degradation	180	52.7%	52.1%
urban environment	180	63.6%	61.7%

Table 38: First classifier details (Catalan)

Classes	# examples	Precision	Recall
relevant	1500	85.7%	82.1%
irrelevant	1500	83.4%	86.8%

Table 39: Second classifier details (Catalan)

Second classifier	# examples	Precision	Recall
ecology	180	48.9%	49.2%
eco-efficiency	180	61.2%	61.0%
climate change	220	70.4%	71.2%
waste	200	54.1%	53.8%
water protection	200	45.6%	44.4%
environmental policy	160	60.3%	56.7%
land degradation	180	53.4%	52.0%
urban environment	180	63.9%	59.3%

Table 40: List of keywords for post retrieval for each concept

ecology	ecosystem,preservation,conservation,habitat,natural capital,biological classification,biodiversity,pollution,wildlife,environmental interventions,fauna,flora,rainforest protection ,wetlands,Natura 2000,bioretention,protected species,ecological status,ecosystem,natural habitat,eco system,ecotourism,bioconcentration,biochemical
eco-efficiency	biomass ,geothermal power,solar energy ,hydroelectric power,photovoltaic ,energy conservation ,clean energy,ecological footprint ,energy consumption,renewable energy sources,energy market,eco balance,sustainability,eco labels,energy saving,eco fund,externalities,biomass ,biofuels,ecological footprint ,resource efficiency,dirty fuels,geothermal,solar panels,biofuel,renewables,wind energy,alternative energy,thermal

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

	energy,biodegradable,biogas
climate change	greenhouse gases,carbon dioxide,global warming,emissions,greenhouse effect,atmosphere,low-carbon,zero emissions,industrial emissions,air pollution,global environment,aerosol,acid rain,atmospheric emission,photochemical pollution,carbon footprint
waste	recycling,waste,waste management,waste water,waste disposal,waste hazardous,waste solid,plastic pollution,waste treatment,waste transfer,waste removal,urban waste,waste services,waste plant,nuclear waste,waste collection,industrial waste,hazardous waste,toxic waste,medical waste,household waste,waste regulations,electronic waste,chemical treatment,clinical waste,combustion residue,battery disposal,composting,compost
water protection	drinking water,water treatment,water quality,groundwater protection,flood risk management,water scarcity,water reuse,clean water,hydrological pressures,water information,eutrophication,water resource,sewage treatment,thermal pollution,water contamination,marine pollution,water pollutants,biochemical oxygen demand,chemical oxygen demand,aquatic ecosystem,sanitary sewer overflows,coastal pollution,water conservation
environmental policy	environmental compliance,environmental audits,environmental permitting,environmental conditions,environmental directives,environmental regulations,european environment agency,environmental accountability,environmental impact assessment ,environmental plan,environmental framework,environmental legislation,environment investigation agency,strategic environmental assessment,environmental law,environmental law
land degradation	pesticides,food labels,erosion control,overfishing,overgrazing,food chain,nutrients,carbon cycle ,nitrogen cycle ,phosphorus cycle ,agroecology,soil contaminants,fertilizers,irrigation water,crop residues,landscape ecology,desertification ,deforestation

Table 41: Influential accounts based on their incoming degree

Username	Link	In- degree
@gazzema	Communication Adviser @EU_Commission @Energy4Europe @ristori20•#Energy #H2020 #SmartCities #SETPlan #Tw4SE #SETPlan17 Coaching staff https://t.co/e4QMyze4w7	2808
@stracma	Head of Unit New #energy techs & #innovation @EU_Commission @Energy4Europe #EnergySystem #SmartCities #SmartGrid #EnergyStorage #SETPlan #SETPlan17 RT#endors	2617
@HansLak	Accelerating the #GlobalGoals #SDGs #2030now Catalyst for social #innovation and #transformation @PostNormalEra Let's connect on LinkedIn	1824
@EUSciComm	Promoting #EUSciComm news and views and #womeninSTEM. Focused on the EU funding programme #Horizon2020 (#H2020), not EU affiliated, managed by @garybridgeman.	1663
@EU_eGov	European Commission, CONNECT 'eGovernment & Trust', wking on Digital Public Services and ICT-enabled Public Sector Innovation (RT not endorsement)	1632
@energycoin	Welcome! We build the EnergyCoin \$ENRG community based value platform @efc4u #energyefficiency #renewables #smartgrid #p2p #energystorage maintained @insidestat	1488
@EU_GreenCapital	The official European Green Capital and European Green Leaf Award. Our aim is to improve Europe's urban environment. Tweets by EGCA and EGLA Secretariat.	1299
@EU_opendata	Official account of the EU Open Data Portal (https://t.co/S55H1P74hd) and of #EUOpenData policy. Co-organising #EUdatathon2017 with @EU2017EE	1281
@TeachSDGs	A global movement of teachers pledging to #TeachSDGs; a Task Force of volunteers partnered with the UN to serve @TheGlobalGoals & @TheWorldsLesson. Join us.	1180
@Impakterdotcom	Magazine about Culture, Style, Society with articles by our Team & Global Leaders from UnitedNations, Institutes, NGO. Focus: #SDGs #Tech #Health #Style ...	1176
@EU_H2020	The official account for the EU's #H2020 research and innovation programme. Managed by DG Research & Innovation. Follow Commissioner @moedas too.	1167
@wellbelove	Frequent smiler, marketer, professionally qualified social media expert, presenter, speaker, geek, Lambeth councillor, former Mayor and Parliament candidate.	1164
@Pietervschie	Solving #Young #Jobs Puzzle Chief Exec.MD Werkcenter Int.Chairman @LVV_FF	1088

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

	#EU & #Employment Expert Multiple Award Winner/drs.Politicologie MA(Leiden University)	
@MarcGuberti	19 Year Old Entrepreneur, Author, Blogger, Digital Marketing Expert, Speaker, Instructor @HootSuite Ambassador, Runner, Dog Lover, Red Sox fan	1067
@RoehrerC	Lead #Results Based Management Specialist, Global #Environment Facility @theGef (tweets are mine, RTs ≠ endorsement) - love what you do & keep smiling!	1018
@JuvenileCrime	GLOBAL YOUTH JUSTICE Champions 1,700+ Volunteer-Driven Youth Justice and Juvenile Justice Diversion Programs called Teen/Youth/Student/Peer Court and Peer Jury.	1006
@kimgarst	Passionate about helping entrepreneurs GROW their biz w/ social & digital media! Keynote speaker, Forbes Top 10 Social Media Influencer. Loves God, FAM & hockey	995
@KushyKush	Paving the way to a 100% clean energy future. Working at Elemental Exceleator & Free Electrons.	960
@SDGActors	SDG Actors is the official Global collation of all organizations and individuals that are taking different steps in advancing the achievements of the SDGs.	931
@guillermo_gross	Este es mi perfil personal. Comprometido con la idea del progreso a base de infinitos cambios infinitesimales.	862
@weADAPT1	Learn Share Connect. weADAPT is your platform 4 sharing new work, finding high quality resources & connecting with #climatechange #adaptation professionals.	849
@TheresaPotratz	Content and social media marketer who helps businesses make money, using Twitter and other platforms.	834
@Ayto_Valdemoro		768
@david_porritt	Doctoral Research Leadership, Coaching, Mentoring, Developing People Consultant Headteacher Speaker Husband, Dad Cyclist & Musician Views Mine	768
@CreativeSage	At Creative Sage™ we live a passionate personal mission to cause the spontaneous combustion of creativity, innovation and compassionate intelligence everywhere.	748
@scientix_eu	European collaboration in #STEM teaching, research and policy. Tweets about projects in STEM, educational technology and #teacher training.	745
@V2020net	Vision2020: The Horizon Network is a platform for companies & research organisations seeking funding from the EU Horizon 2020 programme. Powered by @Crowdhelix	713
@nycinews	The National Youth Council of Ireland represents and supports the interests of voluntary youth organisations & acts on issues that affect young people.	693
@NewEuropeans	We are a civil #rights organisation which champions freedom of movement, non-discrimination & the principle of solidarity in #EU. #Brexit #citizensrights	622
@EURACADEMY	Knowledge transfer in highly specialised domains through accurate, in-depth and intensive training.	604
@SergioParra85	Portavoz y Concejal de Ciudadanos en en Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro.	581
@compromisoclima	Plataforma de acción frente al #CambioClimático. Actuamos para implementar el #AcuerdoDeParís y lograr el #ODS13.	580
@wildlifetrav	On a mission to see the world's wildlife. My fave animals are zebras, lions, rhinos and eagles. What are yours?	577
@jobclubsnetwork	The partnership Jobclubsnetwork is Co-funded by Erasmus+ & run by Italy, Portugal, Greece, Bulgaria & Holland https://t.co/JVOgluay75	575
@Way2Learn2Work	The project Way 2 Learn 2 Work tackles youth unemployment & is cofunded by the EU /Lifelong Learning Programme Leonardo da Vinci	545
@smart_akis	Smart Farming Thematic Network. Embracing Smart Farming in Europe. #smartfarming #digitalfarming #smartagriculture #precisionag #AgTech #EIPAgri #H2020	538
@_geoengineering	Concerned about the Health and Environmental Risks of GeoEngineering, SRM and Weather Modification	486
@climateurope	The Europe-wide climate services network for researchers, suppliers & users of climate information. Funded by the European Commission @EU_H2020 #climateservices	480
@top5mundo	Site com os melhores top 5	426
@E2District	#Horizon2020 R & I Project #EnergyEfficient Optimised #DistrictHeating&Cooling #DHC. @NimbusCentre @CIT_ie #UTRC #Veolia #CSTB #Acciona #Tw4SE @PBTINimbus	403

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

@FreeTimePays	With passion and intent, we connect with inspirational people and inspire communities to tackle the issues that help change people's lives for ever.	393
@smarticipate	The Horizon 2020 funded #smarticipate project aims to use open data to give citizens the information needed to shape their city. https://t.co/PI0hGqe9lj	348
@mabhishek45	Blogger, Co-Founder & CEO @beluga_solar, Manufacturing solar products to help people use #solarpower to get #cleanenergy & save the earth from #climatechange	329
@EU_BINGO	Bringing #innovation to ongoing #water management ➡️ a better future under #climatechange 🌱 👥 @EUClimateAction @EU_H2020 #climateadaptation	328
@CERTHellas	CERTH is one of the leading research centres in Greece & listed among the TOP-20 E.U. institutions with the highest participation in competitive research grants	326
@vickalogirou	not settle on one path #Tech #ICT #eGOV #LSPs #science #cybersec #Data #comms #web #EC #DSM #market #IoT #interop #FutureOfWork #innov #DigitalNomad #DigitWorld	324
@jhdez32	Marine and Maritime R&D&I initiatives and infrastructures-Personal View-	321
@intellitics	We're a digital engagement company based in San José, CA (USA). We engage communities and stakeholders through the effective use of technology.	307
@nessmul18	Youth Worker with @foroige Graduate in Community & Youth from @MaynoothUni @nycinews #rep to the @youth_forum Advocate 4 the @SDGchallenge #YoungVoices	307
@SaveRefrigerator	SaveRefrigerator, una manera de ayudar al medio ambiente.	305
@SENSE4USproject	R&D project. Creating web-based tools to support policy makers gather relevant info for policies, simulate effects of #policy proposals & determine sentiments	289

Table 42: Most influential users that do not follow STEP account

Username	Link	Followers	#STEP followers
@6BillionPeople	Looking for the best artist in the world! All Genres, All Artist. The #Musicindustrycontest ends Oct 27th 2017! submit your best two songs. Click link in my bio	4460787	16
@DigitalTrendsDigitalTrends	Tech for the way we live. Facebook & Instagram: @DigitalTrends	1924348	11
DennisKoutoudis	Entrepreneur Founder & CEO of https://t.co/2ene73iUD3 Influential LinkedIn Expert International Keynote Speaker Author	1782972	10
@johnrampton	Entrepreneur and connector. Founder of @Due. I blog about my successes and epic failures for @Entrepreneur @TechCrunch and @Mashable #fintech	1538495	11
@AskAaronLee	Regional Manager APAC @agorapulse. Trying to perfect the art of cappuccino. Introvert with awesome hair. https://t.co/PZNF06OICy ✉️ hi@askaaronlee.com	1118753	13
@drjoyce_knudsen	#SeniorFashionista Creator Global Style System #ImpressionManagement Podcast Radio PsychToday Women's Day Glamour #TrueGiver https://t.co/Xk2JiDXfZY	1117163	13
@StartupPro	Veteran startup mentor, executive, blogger, author, tech professional, and Angel investor. Published on Forbes, Entrepreneur, Inc, Huffington Post, and others.	1024491	11
@LeadToday	Improving the Sales Profession, Developing the Next Generation of Leaders, Not selling a thing on Twitter, only giving back.	994978	14
@annemariayrityis	Anne-Maria Yrityis™ Social Media Influencer Thought Leader I am a leader: I (un)follow back. #IFB. FREE leadership tips @leadingwithpassion dot org	660008	15
@MikeSchiemer	Frugal Entrepreneur Digital Marketing Manager Investor Top 100 Social Media Influencer Author of The \$10 Digital Media Startup: https://t.co/6QzPM0vsOU	233693	14
@RNFinfo	Ciudadano Citizen, Former Science and Technology Communications Advisor	179362	10
@Esri	Esri users create maps that run the world. #ArcGIS an open platform for #GIS #3D #Imagery #Apps #IoT #Cities #BigData #Geodesign #TheScienceofWhere	153249	10

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

@evankirstel	#Influencer #ThoughtLeader Helping #B2B clients w #SocialMediaMarketing in #Enterprise #IoT #Telecom #Security #Cloud and #DigitalHealth at https://t.co/Y9NQcCGUp7	152489	11
@CECHR_UoD	Centre for Environmental Change & Human Resilience: Main themes: Food Water Energy Health Sustainability Ecology Environmental Economic & Social Well-being	146620	12
@SimonCocking	Senior editor @Irish_TechNews #1 Irish tech site Editor in chief @TodayCrypto #TEDx @sundaybusiness @IrishTimes @SouthernStarIRL #blockchain #FinTech #ICO	112630	14
@stbaasch	Architect @ladiesinside - The digital city of women entrepreneurs.	111671	17
@Scientists4EU	Love UK-EU science EU FB page: https://t.co/sVb7nTZOtK SfEU twibbon: https://t.co/debp3TSAVR	81845	13
@EU_Regional	EU Regional & Urban Policy. Policy developments & results. #ESIFunds #CohesionPolicy https://t.co/7OIGsEKdND #EUinmyRegion @CorinaCretuEU. RT#endrsmt	66221	24
@JasonLRobinson	Founder & CEO, Sustainability Television... and a few other things. Check out https://t.co/9A8KRcsjxk or on YouTube: https://t.co/yl2HM6vuyt ↕	65437	13
@UNUWIDER	Providing economic analysis and policy advice to promote sustainable and equitable development for all. #UNGOALS	57473	10
@fasttrackimpact	Fast track your research impact. Improve your productivity. Tips & training for researchers by researchers. Tweets by @profmarkreed	42547	12
@energyenviro	Daily news on sustainable energy, circular economy, bioeconomy, environment, cleantech, startups, tourism - active in Twitter since August 2015	40015	10
@EU_MARE	The official account for @EU_Commission Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). Marine/maritime/seafood news. Rts and likes not necessarily endorsements.	31346	32
@THEnergyNet	"#RENEWABLES& #MINING" #RenewableEnergy on ISLANDS" #MICROGRIDS#MINIGRIDS#OFFGRID#SOLAR #PV#WIND#HYBRID#SUSTAINABILITY #CLIMATE #EnergyStorageConsulting"	20473	10
@CORDIS_EU	Official CORDIS account. News and information on EU-funded research projects & results #FP7 #Horizon2020 #CORDISpacks #ribfp7 #researcheu #h2020	18994	20
@GreenHeatEU	EEIP Twitter account for industrial sustainable heat and cold solutions. #wasteheat #cogeneration #districtheating #heatpumps - EEIP general news @GreenCogEU	18282	11
@S_Analysts	We are Agile Software Artisans, Offer #Web #Mobile #Cloud & #IoT Solutions at one place. https://t.co/ZONKlyC72b	17873	10
@WYeates	Climate & Envirotweeting. Freelance digital communications consultant. MSc Environmental Technology	17544	10
@SoonfeedEU	Indie feed of European ideas, people & events before they go live. We make & break stories beforetime. Curators @happeningo @Soonfeed. Team #TheEuropeSong.	14509	15
@brandobenifei	Europarlamentare PD/S&D	13159	10
@Vattel	Since 2010, we've helped our clients build their social media influence & visibility in Brussels - and elsewhere. Love to collaborate #Tw4SE	12363	12
@robvank	Founder of #IoT Council	12069	11
@EUFIC	European Food Information Council. Food facts for healthy choices. For news from European research projects @SciFoodHealth	10430	13
@watify	Watify is the European Union initiative inspiring and helping traditional businesses in their technological transformation.	10176	14
@EEFinancing	Dedicated #EEIP Twitter channel for news about financing #energyefficiency and @icpeurope #EEFIG General news @GreenCogEU & @EEIPenMg	9523	15
@garybridgeman	Coach for women in STEM and EU affairs (men can also apply), mindfulness teacher, ACT, dad, stepdad, scicomm writer, story gamer, amongst other things	9379	17
@GUEGUENDaniel	Head of #strategy & #lobbying of @PACTEurope, Visiting Professor at the @collegeofeurope and @BlogActiv blogger. Tweets are personal. RT#endorsement	9308	18

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

@EnergyDemand	EiD is a sustainable energy blog from Europe, edited by Rod Janssen, a sustainable energy expert based in Paris & London. #energyefficiency	8470	21
@EKTgr	Εθνικό Κέντρο Τεκμηρίωσης: Ανοικτή Πρόσβαση στη γνώση, ψηφιακό επιστημονικό περιεχόμενο, National Documentation Centre: Open Access to scientific content	4638	11
@ESS_Survey	Monitoring Social Change in Europe since 2002 The European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ESS ERIC) is a biennial survey	3879	10
@EUAtlantic	The Atlantic Action Plan (AAP) aims to revitalise the marine and maritime economy in the EU Atlantic area. A project funded by the European Commission.	3662	10
@EU_Funds	EU Funds, Financial Instruments of the EU, EU Programmes, #H2020, #FP7 and #FP9, Training courses on EU project design and implementation	3471	17
@SciFoodHealth	Food and health news from European research collaborations. Bringing the latest science to you! #H2020	3349	12
@H2020Manuals	Helping great ideas achieve their potential - A series of hands-on guidebooks for writing winning Horizon 2020 grant proposals.	3255	17
@EU_events	EU Events is the web portal gathering all EU-related events in Brussels. Follow us on all social media using the hashtag #EUEvents !!	3111	10
@Welcomeurope	18 years experienced on European Grants Training, Monitoring and Consultancy #EU #Europe #funding Tel: +33 1 42 54 60 64 contact@welcomeurope.com	2240	22
@euagenda	Your hub for all things EU #EUagenda Publish your Conferences, PDFs, Videos for free. Start at https://t.co/PSQq1TsClh	2015	11
@DunavNET	Turnkey IoT solutions for Smart Cities, Smart Manufacture & Smart Agriculture; Digital transformation Consultancy; Research & Development; Microsoft IoT partner	1854	10
@NETME_IN	NETME-IN is co-funded by the #Erasmus+ Programme with #EU partners from #France #Italy #Croatia #Holland & #Turkey, building a Digital Pro Identity #DPI	1790	11
@DFOIW2W	St. Dutch Foundation of Innovation Welfare 2 Work is a (#Youth) #Employment, Welfare to #Work & #Entrepreneurship expert. Projects co-funded by #EU /#Erasmus+	1392	11
@PavlosDoikos	#innovation, #SMEs, #EU #environmental policy & funding programmes (e.g. #LIFE, #Horizon2020), #climate, #energy #circulareconomy, green financing & business.	1273	13
@EESC_TEN	@EU_EESC Section working 2 make voices of Europe's #civsoc heard concerning #Energy #Transport #DigitalSociety #ServicesofGeneralInterest	1159	15
@H2020_KATANA	KATANA accelerator aims to support all European start-ups and SMEs in the #agrifood, #ICT sector or raising emerging technologies! #Horizon2020	1028	10
@IoF2020	#IoF2020 facilitates the uptake of #IoT in the European food & farming sector • Funded under #H2020 • Grant agreement no. 731884 • https://t.co/IFF1ZCxfFH	1027	11
@Dr_PMichalis	Scientist/Engineer - Marie-Curie #Research Fellow #SHM #Sensors #Bridge #Dam #SmartInfrastructure #Hazards #Geophysics #GeoEngineering #AssetManagement	1014	22

Table 43: Top 50 users based on the number of relevant tweets they posted

Username	Rel. Tweets (%)	Communiy	description
@aprxtweet	87	Italian (Locride)	Communication strategist, press officer and journalist. #green #sustainability #smartcity #sostenibilità #comunicazione Amo il buon cibo, adoro cucinarlo.
@globalyouth	84	SDGs and Climate Change	Global Youth Action Network: Youth. Participation. Collaboration. Action
@EnergyBoom	82	SDGs and Climate Change	Tweeting the latest renewable energy, environment and clean tech news!

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

@CarbonXprint	79	SDGs and Climate Change	Translating concern for climate change into measurable and profitable action. Ask us how!
@FreeReporter	77	Italian (Locride)	Collaborative #journalism on #environment, #sustainability and #conflicts / #Giornalismo collaborativo su #ambiente, #sostenibilita e #conflitti
@reducepollution	73	SDGs and Climate Change	Official twitter account of the Pollution news and environmental information website http://t.co/lzISrPrThK
@FreeSolarFarms	73	SDGs and Climate Change	Renewable Energy, Solar Power, Solar Energy, Solar Panels, PV, EV, Solar Farms, Wind Power, Photovoltaics, Internet, SEO, Fishing, Comedy, Live Music, Live Dead
@Climate_Science	72	Italian (Locride)	Be the change – create a green economy by following the latest independent news about climate science & the UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).
@GreenDiwali2017	71	SDGs and Climate Change	Joining hands from this Diwali to clean up the once most beautiful parts of the city- Lakes 9717064159/8585952994
@GIN_GROUP	71	Italian (Locride)	GIN GROUP e' distribuzione e rivendita di prodotti per Energia alternativa, Risparmio Energetico, Edilizia Innovativa. Richieste a network@gingroup.it
@ENERGIALIMPIA21	69	Catalan (Mollet)	SIGUENOS Y TE SEGUIMOS
@phervas	67	Spanish (Valdemoro)	Lo mejor está por llegar...
@BayshoreRecycle	67	Turkish (Hatay)	Full service & award winning recycling facility in NJ. Environmental leader and WBE in NJ and NY. Go green with us!
@TreesUganda	65	SDGs and Climate Change	Planting Trees in Uganda UG Giving mother nature 🌱🌱🌱 a fighting chance against Destruction Together 🤝 we can revive mother nature's 🌱🌱🌱 heartbeat
@S_Cavaliere	64	SDGs and Climate Change	#BreatheLife @CCACoalition
@EnvAm	63	SDGs and Climate Change	Environment America is a federation of citizen-funded organizations that advocate for clean air, clean water, and open spaces in 29 states and Washington, D.C.
@kevinmnichols	63	SDGs and Climate Change	#KidsHealth #Science #ClimateChange #Facts #Environment #Education #Travel #HealthCare #Alzheimers
@cammosher	62	SDGs and Climate Change	Teaching geology at Salt Lake Community College. Concerned about Climate Change. Member of Citizens Climate Lobby.
@GreenCollarGuy	61	SDGs and Climate Change	Dedicated to supporting the business of sustainability. You'll wonder how I find so many important sustainability articles to share. Follow me today.
@GreenSteve_com	61	Italian (Locride)	I'm a green blogger who hopes to educate and motivate people to make the small and big changes to their lifestyle to reduce their carbon footprint
@LexisUK_Enviro	61	SDGs and Climate Change	What's new in #environmental #law? Updates brought to you by LexisPSL Environment—practical guidance for environmental lawyers.
@jasonsorter	61	SDGs and Climate Change	Western States Public Affairs Professional
@GENINews	60	SDGs and Climate Change	Global Energy Network Institute focuses on interconnection of electric power networks between nations with an emphasis on tapping renewable energy resources.
@TreeBanker	60	SDGs and Climate Change	CEO & Co-Founder @CLIME_IT -Advocate for Businesses Creating Value in the Low-Carbon Economy
@BerendJanKleutere	60	SDGs and Climate Change	Deeply passionate about Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC), co-founder and CTO @BlueriseBV and #OTEC researcher at @TUDelft
@BrianSchmidly	60	SDGs and Climate Change	Thought Leader on Sustainability, Energy and Climate Change in Latin America & Caribbean DESERTEC Solar & Energy Storage Project Developer LEED AP
@EnergyMrktPrice	59	Italian (Locride)	Digital Energy & Risk Management SaaS Solutions for Utilities/ Energy Consultants/ I&C #EnergyCockpit ☐
@TSolarPV	58	Catalan (Mollet)	T-Solar, uno de los principales productores independientes de energía, gestiona 286MWp en España, Italia, India, Perú, EEUU, Puerto Rico, Japón y México

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

@davidorreta	58	Catalan (Mollet)	Periodista especializado en gestión de residuos en @ResiduosPro. ¿Sabes lo que se hace con tu basura? Reduce, Reutiliza, Recicla y, siempre, Reflexiona
@PaulGosling	58	SDGs and Climate Change	Sustainability recruitment specialist since 1995. Providing recruitment support to the #Environmental and #Sustainability sector. Coach for @WimbornerFC U14s.
@greenmover2012	58	SDGs and Climate Change	CO2-sequestration advocate
@_cheerfulgiving	57	SDGs and Climate Change	Revolutionizing philanthropy with technology that empowers big-hearted people to unfold the greater good. Join the movement.
@NatureClimate	57	SDGs and Climate Change	A monthly journal covering the science of climate change, its impacts and wider implications for the economy, society and policy. Tweets by Bronwyn
@bluecamas	56	SDGs and Climate Change	Sustainable Building Consultant in British Columbia, Canada.
@Syntegra101	56	SDGs and Climate Change	Multi-award winning specialist energy and low carbon building solutions provider with offices in the UK and UAE
@ClimateReality	56	SDGs and Climate Change	Founded by @algore, we're bringing the world together to stop climate change and create a healthy and prosperous future powered by clean energy.
@fundaprvh	56	Turkish (Hatay)	DIRECTOR GENERAL Y EDITOR EN JEFE DE FUNDap
@MJohnsonChase	55	SDGs and Climate Change	Adventurer, Writer, Theatre Director, Entrepreneur, See https://t.co/E7JNhNSo8w for more. #climatefiction #cleanenergy #adventurecycling #climatechange
@fondazioneecs	55	Italian (Locride)	Centre for a Sustainable Future aims to capture the public's attention on environmental issues, sustainable development, and climate change
@larsling	55	SDGs and Climate Change	Inspires people, companies & cities to become 100% Renewable by delivering Nordic Climate Impact solutions, financing & leadership. https://t.co/Ejz8Latd6h
@greennetworksco	55	SDGs and Climate Change	IT #outsourcing company and #1 in the #MiddleEast with combined power of Green #Hosting, #Cloud Computing & Efficient IT Services & Solutions.
@cecberg	55	Italian (Locride)	journalist, communication consultant, #socialmedia expert, media relations on energy, renewable energy and environment.
@Envirobama	54	Italian (Locride)	What is the Obama administration's record on the environment?
@GlobalCanopy	54	SDGs and Climate Change	Accelerating the transition to a deforestation-free global economy
@uscan	54	SDGs and Climate Change	U.S. Climate Action Network (USCAN) is the largest network of organizations focused on climate change in the U.S.
@ejfoundation	54	SDGs and Climate Change	Help us fight for climate refugees. Make leaders #RecogniseRights
@EDFbiz	54	SDGs and Climate Change	Accelerating environmental innovation. Green Business Sustainability CSR ESG. Tweets by @nataliemck18 & @AmyMorse_
@UNEP_EU	53	SDGs and Climate Change	UN Environment Brussels Office. For news, events and publications see: https://t.co/dyOalXAiKu Retweets are not endorsements
@urbanenergy	53	SDGs and Climate Change	Manager, Climate Policy World Bank Views entirely my own!
@BusinessGreen	53	SDGs and Climate Change	The UK's leading web site for green business news and analysis. Follow our team: @James_BG, @Madeleine_BG, @michaelholder

Table 44: Top 5 users that post relevant content per community

Community	Username	Rel. tweets (%)	Description
Italian (Locride)	@apruxtweet	87	Communication strategist, press officer and journalist. #green #sustainability #smartcity #sostenibilità #comunicazione Amo il buon cibo, adoro cucinarlo.
	@FreeReporte	77	Collaborative #journalism on #environment, #sustainability and

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

	r		#conflicts / #Giornalismo collaborativo su #ambiente, #sostenibilita e #conflitti
	@Climate_Science	72	Be the change – create a green economy by following the latest independent news about climate science & the UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).
	@GIN_GROUP	71	GIN GROUP e' distribuzione e rivendita di prodotti per Energia alternativa, Risparmio Energetico, Edilizia Innovativa. Richieste a network@gingroup.it
	@GreenSteve_com	61	I'm a green blogger who hopes to educate and motivate people to make the small and big changes to their lifestyle to reduce their carbon footprint
Spanish (Valdemoro)	@phervas	67	Lo mejor está por llegar...
	@charoal17	27	Concejala Socialista del Ayto de Coslada
	@dhowellseo	26	Environmental governance/gobernanza ambiental @SEO_BirdLife 'Infopini3n' conservation, nature, politics/conservaci3n, naturaleza y pol3tica
	@MahiSide	23	Global politics, EU minutiae, climate, energy and environment. Cheerleader for wind & solar. Let's move #beyondcoal
	@sdelavargalez	21	5a Teniente de Alcalde, Area de Seguridad, P.Civil, Movilidad y Transportes Ayto.Boadilla Monte/Cta.Personal/ ♥ □ la montaña, leer, #Italia y a mi #Atleti
SDGs and Climate Change	@globalyouth	84	Global Youth Action Network: Youth. Participation. Collaboration. Action
	@EnergyBoom	82	Tweeting the latest renewable energy, environment and clean tech news!
	@CarbonXprint	79	Translating concern for climate change into measurable and profitable action. Ask us how!
	@reducepollution	73	Official twitter account of the Pollution news and environmental information website http://t.co/lzISrPrThK
	@FreeSolarFarms	73	Renewable Energy, Solar Power, Solar Energy, Solar Panels, PV, EV, Solar Farms, Wind Power, Photovoltaics, Internet, SEO, Fishing, Comedy, Live Music, Live Dead
Greek (Thessaloniki-Crete)	@tkromm	45	Everyone is entitled to their own opinion, but no one is entitled to their own facts
	@lifeclimatree	35	
	@greenpeace_gr	33	Η Greenpeace είναι μία διεθνής μη κερδοσκοπική οργάνωση που με τη δράση της αναδεικνύει τα σημαντικότερα περιβαλλοντικά προβλήματα.
	@protmes	33	
	@NewNet_News	30	For the latest news and insight in the cleantech and renewable energy community
Catalan (Mollet)	@ENERGIALIMPIA21	69	SIGUENOS Y TE SEGUIMOS
	@davidorraeta	58	Periodista especializado en gesti3n de residuos en @ResiduosPro. ¿Sabes lo que se hace con tu basura? Reduce, Reutiliza, Recicla y, siempre, Reflexiona
	@TSolarPV	58	T-Solar, uno de los principales productores independientes de energ3a, gestiona 286MWp en Espa3a, Italia, India, Per3, EEUU, Puerto Rico...
	@IzanGuerrero	49	Periodista @sga_uma PhD por @Infouma Comunicaci3n y Cambio Climático. Amante del fútbol para ciegos, el cine y Cabo de Gata ...
	@climaencrisis	47	#cambioclimatico #climatechange
Turkish (Hatay)	@BayshoreRecycle	67	Full service & award winning recycling facility in NJ. Environmental leader and WBE in NJ and NY. Go green with us!
	@fundaprvh	56	DIRECTOR GENERAL Y EDITOR EN JEFE DE FUNDAP
	@Green_Coast	48	Green Coast Rubbish is an environmentally conscious disposal company. If we're not recycling or donating we're posting waste diversion & environmental content.
	@cevre_muh	41	Çevre Mühendisliđi Paylaşım ve İletişim Portalı / Environmental Engineering // info@cevre Muhendisligi.org // Site Kurucu&Yöneticisi - Gökhan TUFAN //
	@genctema_artvin	41	

Table 45: Top 5 users that post concept related content per concept

Concept	Username	Community	Rel. tweets	Description
Climate change	@globallyouth	SDGs and Climate Change	81	Global Youth Action Network: Youth. Participation. Collaboration. Action
	@EnergyBoom	SDGs and Climate Change	63	Tweeting the latest renewable energy, environment and clean tech news!
	@Climate_Science	Italian (Locride)	52	Be the change – create a green economy by following the latest independent news about climate science & the UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).
	@greenmover2012	SDGs and Climate Change	43	CO2-sequestration advocate
	@airtecnic	Catalan (Mollet)	41	Air Curtain Manufacturer leader in door air curtains of high quality and wide range to cover all applications http://t.co/vl2GS3q3xn
Eco-efficiency	@aprxtweet	Italian (Locride)	86	Communication strategist, press officer and journalist. #green #sustainability #smartcity #sostenibilità #comunicazione Amo il buon cibo, adoro cucinarlo.
	@FreeSolarFarms	SDGs and Climate Change	72	Renewable Energy, Solar Power, Solar Energy, Solar Panels, PV, EV, Solar Farms, Wind Power, Photovoltaics, Internet, SEO, Fishing, Comedy, Live Music, Live Dead
	@GIN_GROUP	Italian (Locride)	71	GIN GROUP e' distribuzione e rivendita di prodotti per Energia alternativa, Risparmio Energetico, Edilizia Innovativa. Richieste a network@gingroup.it
	@phervas	Spanish (Valdemoro)	67	Lo mejor está por llegar...
	@ENERGIALIMPIA21	Catalan (Mollet)	67	SIGUENOS Y TE SEGUIMOS
Ecology	@fundaprvh	Turkish (Hatay)	56	DIRECTOR GENERAL Y EDITOR EN JEFE DE FUNDAP
	@antombazzo83	Italian (Locride)	45	Cambiamenti climatici e politiche ambientali. Appassionato di politica. ex nuotatore, milanista e appassionato di sport.
	@bluecamas	SDGs and Climate Change	39	Sustainable Building Consultant in British Columbia, Canada.
	@biosierra	Catalan (Mollet)	39	Biòlogo, Activista Ambiental. Autor: MODELO SUELO INTELIGENTE. Miembro @ACA_ARBOR Director @Funda_Biosierra PERCEPCIONISTA
	@Fotophysis	SDGs and Climate Change	37	Agenda-free images from the world we share. Physis: (Greek: φύσις) = nature.
Environmental policy	@CorsoLauraConti	Italian (Locride)	39	Da quindici anni Legambiente ed Editoriale La Nuova Ecologia promuovono il Corso EuroMediterraneo di Giornalismo Ambientale Laura Conti
	@_cheerfulgiving	SDGs and Climate Change	37	Revolutionizing philanthropy with technology that empowers big-hearted people to unfold the greater good. Join the movement.
	@childandgreen	SDGs and Climate Change	22	Humanitarian Organization
	@ptflydisc	SDGs and Climate Change	18	RPCV (Borneo 71-73) and Climate Solutions Specialist linking FUN with a healthy planet to create the political will for a stable climate.
	@kevinmnichols	SDGs and Climate Change	17	#KidsHealth #Science #ClimateChange #Facts #Environment #Education #Travel #HealthCare #Alzheimers
Land degradation	@FreeReporter	Italian (Locride)	75	Collaborative #journalism on #environment, #sustainability and #conflicts / #Giornalismo collaborativo su #ambiente, #sostenibilita e #conflitti
	@GlobalCanopy	SDGs and Climate Change	36	Accelerating the transition to a deforestation-free global economy

D4.4: Adaptations to social media monitoring tool

	@cropprotection	Italian (Locride)	34	Securing food supply with crop protection solutions - #WithOrWithout #pesticides? - #ag #food #health #water #biodiversity
	@TreesUganda	SDGs and Climate Change	28	Planting Trees in Uganda UG Giving mother nature 🌱🌱🌱 a fighting chance against Destruction Together 🤝 we can revive mother nature's 🌱🌱🌱 heartbeat
	@OrganicPortal	SDGs and Climate Change	18	Organic Portal - Organic news and comment compiled by Frank Marsland. Please support your Organic Farmers & Producers and Organic Shops
Urban environment	@GreenSteve_com	Italian (Locride)	35	I'm a green blogger who hopes to educate and motivate people to make the small and big changes to their lifestyle to reduce their carbon footprint
	@AlexTsatsou	SDGs and Climate Change	15	Urban Planning & Climate Resilience @ihsrotterdam Erasmus Uni Rotterdam, Netherlands
	@LeadingCities	SDGs and Climate Change	13	Leading Cities is a global leader in advancing Smart City solutions and research. #IoT #SmartCities #GovTech #CivicTech
	@UrbanRefugeeH3	SDGs and Climate Change	12	#UrbanRefugees news on the New Urban Agenda for the #Habitat3 Conference in Quito, #Ecuador and beyond. Curated by @JoshuaAspden
	@simciresilience	SDGs and Climate Change	11	SIM-CI is a high-tech company creating services and tools to make your critical infrastructures future proof; building a sustainable, safer and smarter society.
Waste	@BayshoreRecycle	Turkish (Hatay)	55	Full service & award winning recycling facility in NJ. Environmental leader and WBE in NJ and NY. Go green with us!
	@davidorreata	Catalan (Mollet)	54	Periodista especializado en gestión de residuos en @ResiduosPro. ¿Sabes lo que se hace con tu basura? Reduce, Reutiliza, Recicla y, siempre, ...
	@Social_Plastic	SDGs and Climate Change	35	Social Plastic® is plastic collected by @PlasticBank that has been harvested by the poor/removed from the oceans, beaches or waterways.
	@SocialGoodLife	SDGs and Climate Change	35	Social Good Life is a challenge started by @ShaunFrankson to add or improve one social good habit each week. Change the world with your habits & purchase power.
	@BoatMadeOScotc h	SDGs and Climate Change	33	Another filmmaker trying to save the world with a documentary about #ClimateChange, #Capitalism and the #Collapse of civilization. #biotheism & #ecosocialism FTW
Water protection	@AquaFed	SDGs and Climate Change	36	The International Federation of Private Water Operators
	@CanadianWater	SDGs and Climate Change	32	Your trusted news source for all Canadian water issues. #drinkingwater #wastewater #stormwater #cleantech #indigenous #watersheds https://t.co/gqo8kLSJWw
	@GWPMed	SDGs and Climate Change	29	Working towards a #watersecure Mediterranean
	@MBC230K	SDGs and Climate Change	27	Water risks Climate change resilience (views are my own)
	@lauriefourneaux	SDGs and Climate Change	24	Youth program coordinator at the International Secretariat for Water.

Figure 45: The Sustainable development goals accounts community of the STEP network

Figure 46: The Entrepreneurs - media influencers accounts community of the STEP network

Figure 47: The Greek accounts community of the STEP network

Figure 48: The European projects - Innovation 1 accounts community of the STEP network

Figure 49: The European projects – Innovation B accounts community of the STEP network

Figure 50: The Youth job opportunities accounts community of the STEP network

11 Appendix II

STEP Pilot Questionnaire

This questionnaire will provide us with background information that will help us analyse the answers you give in later stages of this experiment.

User ID:	<input type="text"/>
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Please place an “X” in the box that best matches your opinion. Please answer the questions as fully as you feel able to.

Part 1: Online Experience

	Never	Once or twice a year	Once or twice a month	Once or twice a week	Every day
1.1 Use Facebook?					
1.2. Use Twitter?					
1.3. Use online searching of Twitter?					
1.4. Employ a Twitter tool, such as Tagboard (https://tagboard.com/)					
1.5. What do you use social media for? (list up to three main tasks)					
1.6. If you use Twitter, what do you use it for?					
1.7 Identify your three main sources of information on environmental issues concerning your region					

Part 2: Questionnaire – Main Task

You will be asked to accomplish a task that involves interaction with online tools. Immediately after completing each task, please fill the questionnaire that is reported after the task description

Read the task and execute it to the best of your ability using Twitter, Facebook and other social media, then Tagboard and last Social Tracker. Each of the tasks will take approximately 10 minutes. Immediately after completing each task, please fill the questionnaire that is reported after the task description

Note down your outcome in the field below. Stop either when you have achieved the task or when 10 minutes have elapsed. When you are finished, please complete the questionnaire below.

Assignment: You are a public officer in the city hall looking for further details and information on environmental issues of your interest concerning your region. At the moment you are assigned to search and identify insights on “Περιοχές δικτύου Natura 2000 Κρήτης” dialogue that has emerged in your area.

2.1 Task A: Utilize Facebook, Twitter, Instagram or any social media that you think is of relevance and list three stories/topics related to the main topic, three influencers, three multimedia posts and three of the most recent posts that are the most interesting to you.

2.2 Task B: Use a tool like <https://tagboard.com/> to search for insights based on a topic related hashtags. Again list three stories/topics related to the main topic, three influencers, three multimedia posts and three of the most recent posts that are the most interesting to you.

2.1 Outcome (Task A) – list three topics, three influencers, three multimedia posts and three most recent posts

2.2 Outcome (TagBoard) – list three topics, three influencers, three multimedia posts and three most recent posts

2.3. Generally, I find the Twitter-based services I used (Tagboard) are:

easy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	complicated
interesting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	not interesting
satisfying	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	frustrating
valuable	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	inferior
efficient	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	inefficient
clear	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	confusing
innovative	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	conventional

2.4 Task C: Utilize the Social Tracker tool (http://188.214.128.140/ui/?user_id=Crete) to search for insights on the “Περιοχές δικτύου Natura 2000 Κρήτης” dialogue. Click on the story and leverage the filters’ column on the left to list three stories/topics related to the main topic, three influencers, three multimedia posts and three of the most recent posts that are the most interesting to you.

2.4 Outcome (Social Tracker) – list three topics, three influencers, three multimedia posts and three most recent posts.

2.5. Now click on the Dashboard and provide your assessment. Generally, I find the Dashboard of the Social Tracker as:

easy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	complicated
interesting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	not interesting
satisfying	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	frustrating
valuable	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	inferior
efficient	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	inefficient
clear	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	confusing
innovative	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	conventional

2.6. Are you satisfied with the results? Did you expect to find further insights and information that you didn't? If so what kind of information did you expect?

2.7. Please rate the usefulness of each of the Dashboard widgets:

Social Mix	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timeline	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Heatmap	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Active Users	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Entities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.8. Please rate how understandable is each of the Dashboard widgets:

Social Mix	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timeline	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Heatmap	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Active Users	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Entities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.9. Are the results relevant?

Social Mix	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Timeline	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Heatmap	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Active Users	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Entities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dashboard (overall)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.10. Are the filters useful?

Language	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Topics	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Original	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Type	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Unique	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Date	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.11. Did you observe any issues in the functionality of the system? Are the filters working well?

2.12. Now give an overall free text assessment of the value of these tools. Which was better and why? What might improve the value to you as a public officer?

2.13. Click to visit the STEP Social Media Mining Tool <http://188.214.128.140/ui/specified/> and provide your assessment. Generally, I find the Dashboard of the Social Tracker as:

easy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	complicated
interesting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	not interesting
satisfying	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	frustrating
valuable	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	inferior
efficient	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	inefficient
clear	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	confusing
innovative	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	conventional

STEP School Questionnaire

This questionnaire aims to explore the view of young people on the usability and usefulness of SMMT - A social media analytics tool developed in the framework of STEP | HORIZON 2020, EU Project. Responses to the questionnaire will be stored securely and no personal details will be passed to anyone else.

*Required

I understand the information about how this data will be used and agree to participate in the survey. *

Yes

No

Were you able to find interesting topics related to the environment within SMMT? *

Yes

No

NA

Please use the Feed and Dashboard to fill in the following questions.

Please name 3 environmental topics of your interest. *

Your answer

Please name the 5 top user locations *

Your answer

Please list the 3 most popular concepts *

Your answer

Please list the 3 most active users *

Your answer

To what extent do you agree with the following statements (1: Strongly Disagree - 7: Strongly Agree) *

Overall, I am satisfied with how easy it is to use SMMT

I was able to complete the tasks and scenarios quickly using SMMT

I believe I could become productive quickly using SMMT

Whenever I made a mistake using the system I could recover easily and quickly

The organization of information on the SMMT screens was clear

The interface was pleasant

I can count on the information I get on this system

The information on this system is valuable

The results are very relevant to my search

Filters work great

I will likely suggest SMMT to a friend

Overall, I am satisfied with how easy it is to use SMMT

I was able to complete the tasks and scenarios quickly using SMMT

I believe I could become productive quickly using SMMT

Whenever I made a mistake using the system I could recover easily and quickly

The organization of information on the SMMT screens was clear

The interface was pleasant

I can count on the information I get on this system

The information on this system is valuable

The results are very relevant to my search

Filters work great

I will likely suggest SMMT to a friend

How satisfied are you with the information presented on the following widgets:
(1: Very Dissatisfied - 7: Very Satisfied) *

Feed

Social Mix

Timeline

Heatmap

Users Locations

Active Users

Entities

Feed

Social Mix

Timeline

Heatmap

Users Locations

Active Users

Entities

If you were to review SMMT what score would you give it out of 10? *

What do you find most frustrating about SMMT? *

Your answer

What do you like best about SMMT?

Your answer

Demographics

Gender: *

Male

Female

Gender Neutral